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METOCEAN AND COASTAL ZONE MONITORING IN HARBOUR REGIONS USING SATELLITE RADAR

COASTMON

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SUMMARY

A. Highlights

- Retrieval of high resolution wind fields for coastal waters from SAR images
- Wave mapping in near coastal regions by means of SAR-derived wave spectra
- Wind and wave climatology from altimeter data
- Application of SAR bathymetry on the Irish coast
- Use of GIS technology for display and analysis of EO data products

B. Objectives

The overall objective of the project was to *explore and test methods for use of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and other new satellite data, and their integration with geographical information systems (GIS), in monitoring environmental/metocean conditions in regions close to harbours trafficked by very large vessels, to improve navigational safety, to aid coastal zone management (CZM), and to improve utilization of satellite observations in the user community.*

C. Context of the work

C.1 Why it is important

The coastal zone and coastal seas are areas of intense human activity where wind, wave and current conditions need to be monitored and forecasted. These areas represent important parts of the economies and transport systems for many countries. Profound alterations have marked coastal seas during the past decades in response to population growth and increasing exploitation of coastal resources. It is an area around which human activity is concentrated, leading to inevitable conflicts among different uses. An important pre-requisite for the sustainable management of coastal resources is the capability to predict change in coastal areas on short as well as long term. This requires an upscaling of the level of coastal marine research, and in particular, the strengthening of the technology and infrastructure for large scale and long term observation of the coastal seas. In view of these considerations [Dronkers, 1995], the creation of a European Coastal Information and Prediction System has been recommended, where remote sensing data will play a crucial role alongside mooring systems with advanced *in situ* sensors.

The importance of coastal regions has been the background for several research and monitoring programmes, such as the Land Ocean Interaction in Coastal Zones (LOICZ) programme within the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP) [LOICZ, 1993]. A coastal zone module is also an integral component of the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), which was established in 1993 by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC), the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO), the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the International Council for Scientific Unions (ICSU), to design and implement a scientifically based system of ocean observations and predictions to fulfill economic, social,

environmental, and scientific objectives. This module has a high priority to many coastal states because of the importance of the coastal area for development and the intimate effects of coastal changes on economic development and human habitation. A global and multi-disciplinary approach is prescribed and the initial emphasis will be on monitoring changes in coastal current and frontal structures. Remote sensing data and particularly SAR data will be of special significance in this phase. GOOS also has a European regional programme called EuroGOOS, where too, the coastal zone is one of the focal regions.

C.2 Who will benefit

Coastal regions near ports, harbours, and other marine terminals are especially prone to environmental hazards owing to heavy traffic by very large crude-oil carriers (VLCCs), towed barges, and other vessels of deep draught and/or restricted manoeuvrability. Navigation in such regions can be difficult and hazardous, and it is critical to have in place an efficient system to monitor relevant metocean and water quality parameters in order to minimize the risk of accidents and to curtail damages in the event of an accident. Some harbour authorities have implemented Vessel Traffic Services (VTS) terminals with responsibilities including: pilotage; safety and regularity of marine traffic; emergency procedures; environmental concerns; communications, shore-to-ship-to-shore; and monitoring and prediction of meteorological and oceanographic (metocean) conditions.

Potential navigational hazards in these regions include harsh weather conditions; dredged channels of limited draught and width; changing bathymetry (e.g. shifting sandbanks); rocky shores and reefs; sudden wind changes; and strong tidal currents. Current fronts and eddies can also cause problems — VLCCs risk navigational drifting due to sudden cross-track current variations — and complex wave phenomena due to bottom refraction, crossing seas, and wave-current interaction, can cause serious accidents (capsizing) even under benign wind conditions.

Some of the processes and parameters which are particularly important in the context of navigational and environmental safety are wind, waves, currents, bathymetry, ocean colour, turbidity, movement of algal blooms, and transport of oil spills and other pollutants. Conventional instruments to measure these parameters can be located only at discrete locations and are not likely to provide the spatial coverage necessary for coastal management applications.

The SAR on the ERS-1 has already shown its capability for detecting ships, oil slicks, and ocean structures related to spatial variability in the current, with promising results in several investigations on detecting and monitoring eddies, fronts, natural and man-made slicks and other ocean surface phenomena. However, further refinement of processing and interpretation techniques, and integration with other types of remote sensing and field data as well as numerical model results is required in order to produce viable products which can be offered to potential users in an operational context.

This project addresses the development of a coastal monitoring system based on satellite data for potential users such as fishing vessels, offshore industry, sea transportation, traffic management, weather forecasting and many others. The incorporation of satellite as well as *in situ* observations into coastal zone management (CZM) plans using GIS technology has proven to be a powerful tool. Data sets on aquaculture sites, fisheries resources, protected and sensitive habitats, navigation and mooring channels, mooring sites, port facilities, and coastal structures could thus all be integrated with remote sensing data.

C.3 Links with other activities

During the COASTMON project, NERSC has developed links to other satellite remote sensing projects carried out for the Research Council of Norway and industrial organisations. As part of a 3-year SAR Strategy Programme funded by the Research Council of Norway, the SAR Wind Algorithm (SWA) was further developed and tested in Norwegian coastal waters, using data obtained in a field experiment in September 1995 [Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998]. This algorithm is based on a relation between the smearing effects in the SAR image and the wind field, and enables wind fields with scales down to a few hundred meters to be derived. Other tasks of the SAR Strategy Programme included, among others, SAR imaging of surface waves and imaging and detection of surface films and oil spills [Espedal *et al.*, 1997] [Johannessen *et al.*, 1997], and results from these activities were also used in the COASTMON project.

Algorithms for oil spill detection in SAR images have been developed in projects conducted for the Norwegian Space Centre (NSC) [Espedal and Wahl, 1999] [Hamre and Espedal, 1997], and other projects funded by the NSC and ESA (European Space Agency), such as a study of synergetic use of infrared, optical and microwave remote sensing data [Miles *et al.*, 1998], and a PRODEX-study of ocean feature observation repeatability [Sandven *et al.*, 1997], have been useful for the COASTMON project. Analysis of ocean conditions in Norwegian waters based on SAR images, with emphasis on fronts and eddies, were carried out for an oil company (A/S Norske Shell) in 1998 [Sandven *et al.*, 1998], and those activities were also related to the COASTMON project.

At DNMI the work in the COASTMON project has been linked with other activities to improve the forecast products for the ocean and coastal areas. The main activities are to improve the numerical models, and to get more observation data both from the ground and from satellites. During the COASTMON period DNMI has changed the operational wave prediction model from the WINCH model to the WAM model. The WAM model is a more advanced model developed by an international group of scientists [WAMDI Group, 1988]. The operational WAM model at DNMI has a horizontal resolution of 50 km. As a part of the COASTMON work the WAM model was set up and tested with 10 km resolution for a smaller area nested into the 50 km version. Since April 1999 DNMI has run a test version of the 10 km WAM model once a day.

An algorithm for assimilation of significant wave heights from the ERS-2 altimeter into the wave model has been modified and implemented in the WAM model. The algorithm was originally developed for the WINCH model [Breivik and Reistad, 1994]. An algorithm to assimilate SAR wave spectra has also been developed and was implemented in the WINCH model [Breivik *et al.*, 1998]. But it was concluded that the assimilation of SAR spectra had only minor influence on the wave model results, mainly due to lack of SAR data and the on average small differences between the inverted SAR spectra and the model first-guess wave spectra. Therefore the assimilation of SAR wave spectra is not running operationally at the moment. The development of assimilation algorithms for the WINCH model was partly funded by the Norwegian Space Centre.

The work to improve the observations systems and numerical models in the coastal areas will continue in the MAST-III project, EuroROSE, where two COASTMON partners (NERSC and DNMI) participate. The EuroROSE project started in October 1998, and in February and March 2000 it will be an experiment outside Fedje with radar measurements of currents and waves, and DNMI will run nested numerical models down to 1 km resolution.

ARGOSS has co-ordinated its contribution to the COASTMON project with several projects that were funded by the Netherlands Remote Sensing Board BCRS. In the DOCKS project, carried out by a consortium including the Delft University of Technology and the offshore consultancy company HMC an online wave climate system was developed. This system, known as CLAMS, enables users from the offshore community to retrieve wind and wave climate assessments via the Internet. These climate estimates are based on satellite observations obtained with several sensors carried on different satellite missions. In the SPEAR project ARGOSS and its partners (KNMI, TNO-FEL, ECMWF) aims to improve the algorithms that are used to retrieve spectral wave information from space-borne SAR observations. As part of this project an extensive validation study has been carried out of wave spectra from the global version of the wave model WAM, and two SAR retrieval algorithms. The results from this study will be published in an international journal [Mastenbroek and de Valk, 1998].

The CRC-UCC has developed links with the ICAMS (Environment and Climate) project, that aims to provide an integrated engineering and scientific system to monitor temperature, turbidity, chlorophyll concentration, and primary production from multiple EO data sources and coincident standard surface measurements. Another project where CRC-UCC has been involved is the development of a GIS based emergency response decision support system commissioned by Shannon Estuary Ports Authority. The principal aim of this project will be the development of an emergency response decision support system for the Shannon Estuary. In the event of an incident the system will facilitate the rapid deployment of emergency response measures by enabling the user to have instant access to all the available environmental, legislative and administrative information relevant to the particular incident.

An Oil Spill Response Network in the Irish Sea is under preparation, and CRC-UCC has during the COASTMON project been in contact with users to determine their needs for information. The occurrences in 1997 and 1998 of oil spills in the Irish and Celtic Seas, including spills in Dublin Port, Cork Harbour and the Irish Sea, in addition to the 1996 Sea Empress disaster at Milford Haven, focus the need for an integrated approach to oil spill response from the authorities and agencies on both sides of the Irish Sea. With oil refineries in Cork Harbour and Milford Haven (one of the largest refineries in Europe), and increasing traffic in the Irish Sea routes, the establishment of a network to facilitate vertical and horizontal flow of information and expertise would assist operators to maximise response efficiency at any time.

The Irish Sea is an ecologically sensitive area characterised by relatively dense East/West commercial traffic between Ireland and Wales and North/South traffic to and from NW England, Northern Ireland and the Clyde. There is in addition a considerable amount of fishing activity, an ever-increasing fleet of leisure craft and a number of offshore platforms and rigs. The East/West trade is growing at an unprecedented rate. In the competitive scramble to establish a sea-bridge between Ireland and Wales the ferries that are being used, their size, type and speed, are pushing modern technology to its limits. The economic benefits to the two communities are visible, tangible and undisputed. However, marine casualties in the Irish Sea are a matter of major concern; there has been a proliferation in the number of casualties to small fishing boats and pleasure craft and occasional calamitous events that result in loss of life, damage to the environment and set-back to commercial activity. There is a need to strengthen the marine safety/emergency response services. CRC-UCC are undertaking a scientific assessment of the probabilities and extent of the risks with the view to optimal deployment of resources, in the RACER (Risk Assessment and Collaborative Emergency Response in the Irish Sea) project.

D. Summary of results

The most important result achieved by NERSC is the SAR wind algorithm which has been developed, tested and evaluated for Norwegian coastal waters. This method to derive the wind speed from SAR data is based on the spectral properties of the image. The SAR wind algorithm (SWA) proposed by Vacon *et al.* [Vachon *et al.*, 1994] and further examined by Chapron *et al.* [Chapron *et al.*, 1995] and Korsbakken *et al.* [Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998], is based on a relation between the smearing effects [Hasselmann and Shemdin, 1982] in the SAR image and the wind field. Smearing effects tend to increase the coherence (correlation) length of the radar returns in the spatial image domain and to influence the spectral properties of the SAR image. The SWA is derived from a comparison of ERS SAR wave-mode data and the ERS wind scatterometer data which can be simultaneously acquired with the same satellite. When the direction of the wind is determined, the distribution of the wind speed is calculated from the power of the back scattered radar signal in a similar fashion as is done with the scatterometer. The wind direction can also be estimated from the CMOD4 model for different incidence angles, provided the wind speed, derived from the SWA method, can be associated with the corresponding measured radar backscatter (σ^0).

NERSC has also investigated use of SAR wave spectra in near coastal regions of Norway and Ireland. The SAR wave spectra can resolve the long wave part with wavelengths above 100 m, and identify wave refraction and other modification of the wave field near the coasts which are not resolved with standard wave forecasting models.

In addition to wave spectra, SAR data have also been used to investigate current fronts and mesoscale eddies off the coast of Norway. Eddies are important because they represent maximum velocities which are important for navigation of large tankers into the oil terminals near Bergen. Finally, NERSC has performed case studies of sea surface temperature and water colour with infrared and optical satellite data. In many cases, it is beneficial to combine use of SAR with other satellite data to obtain optimal information about metocean conditions.

DNMI has developed a high resolution current model, with resolution of 4 km, which can resolve some of the mesoscale circulation patterns off the coast of Norway. The mesoscale model results have been operatively compared with SAR observations. The detailed ocean fronts and current patterns in SAR images are not found in the model simulations. Better high resolution models need to be developed before SAR-observed current features can be simulated.

DNMI has used its operational wind and wave model for the Norwegian coastal waters in cases where SAR images have been obtained for comparison with SAR-derived wind estimates and SAR-derived wave spectra. SAR wave spectra have previously been developed for operational use in wave forecasting in the open ocean. In this project, NERSC has shown that the main advantage of SAR wave information is near the coast where existing wave models have too coarse resolution to resolve details of the wave field.

Comparison between SAR-derived wind speed estimated by NERSC and wind predictions from DNMI shows good agreement for the case studies performed off the coast of Norway. DNMI and NERSC have performed demonstration of wind, wave and current forecast in combination with SAR data and coastal radar data for the coastal station in Fedje. The combination of these techniques are considered to be an optimal solution to get wind, wave and current information in this area.

The main thrust of ARGOS's efforts in the COASTMON project has been towards the com-

mercialisation of the on-line wave climate system CLAMS. Traditionally, wave climate estimates rely heavily on satellite altimeter records. This instrument is capable of measuring the significant wave height, but it yields no information on the period or direction of the waves. From the user workshop that was held in the first phase of the project it became clear that users have a great need for spectral wave climate data. The only source of spectral wave climate data with a global coverage is the ERS-1/2 SAR, operating in its wave mode. To make use of these SAR observations, about 4 million have been collected to date, a retrieval algorithm is needed. ARGOSS has developed and validated such an algorithm. This method, named SPRA, is capable of retrieving spectral wave data from the SAR measurement without relying on a priori information. The method has been applied to about 1 million wave observations located in the oceans's margins. The resulting spectral wave information has been used to augment the wave climate information in the CLAMS system.

To study the transition of swell spectra entering coastal water, the SPRA retrieval algorithm has also been applied to SAR images of coastal regions. In the COASTMON project this technique to study wave dynamics has been demonstrated in two regions: in the Dutch and in the Irish coastal waters. The technique is capable of tracking a swell system as it approaches the coast. Both the changes in wavelength and the reduction of the energy could be clearly detected in the two demonstrations.

Finally ARGOSS has implemented a version of its Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) that is specifically designed to improve the quality of Admiralty charts. In collaboration with CRC-UCC, this technique has been demonstrated in an area to the South East of Ireland, near the city of Rosslare. The main bathymetric features that were visible in the three ERS SAR images that were acquired coincided with those on the Admiralty chart of the region. The BAS system was capable of retrieving the location, size and length of sand dunes that were captured by the SAR.

The main results of CRC-UCC work has been in to demonstrate different methods of using satellite data to obtain metocean information in Irish waters. These demonstrations have been possible through cooperation with the other partners. CRC-UCC has developed further GIS applications for coastal zones where use of satellite data was not previously included. Through COASTMON, several types of satellite data and derived products have been demonstrated in GIS systems. CRC-UCC has close contact with all main users of coastal ocean data in Ireland, through links to other projects such as ICAMS (Environment and Climate), GIS development for the Shannon Estuary Ports Authority, establishment of an Oil Spill Response Network in the Irish Sea, and the Risk Assessment and Collaborative Emergency Response in the Irish Sea (RACER) project. The results of the COASTMON project has been presented to users at workshops and training courses in Ireland.

The overall results of COASTMON is that a number of applications of satellite data to derive metocean information for coastal waters have been developed, improved and demonstrated for a wide range of users. Most of these applications will remain at demonstration level until satellite data, especially SAR, becomes available with better temporal and spatial resolution which is required for operational use. With RADARSAT and ENVISAT data, the SAR coverage required for coastal waters is gradually improving.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Objectives

The overall objective of the project was to *explore and test methods for use of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and other new satellite data, and their integration with geographical information systems (GIS), in monitoring environmental/metocean conditions in regions close to harbours trafficked by very large vessels, to improve navigational safety, to aid coastal zone management (CZM), and to improve utilization of satellite observations in the user community.*

B. Context

The background for COASTMON is the growing need in the user community to obtain timely and reliable metocean information in coastal waters combined with new possibilities to utilize increasing amounts of satellite data which can provide data on meteorological and oceanographical conditions. The project explored and tested methods to be used for monitoring coastal water areas with different satellite remote sensing data. These methods include synthetic aperture radar and satellite altimeter observations, including those of wave height, current shear zones, wave-current interaction processes, and wind speed and direction, and it is aimed to integrate these observations into coastal monitoring, contingency planning, and planning of multi-user activities, using geographical information systems (GIS).

EO data which are suitable for use in coastal waters include:

- Thermal infra-red images from AVHRR and ATSR provide sea-surface temperature including ocean fronts and water masses and current patterns.
- Visible / near infrared images from AVHRR/ATSR, SeaWifs, MOS, Landsat, SPOT. The data can be used for measuring water colour, including suspended particulate matter and biological activity. Landsat and SPOT have very good resolution which is required along the coastline, but is less important away from the coast (≈ 20 km).
- Radar altimeter data can be used to determine significant wave height and wind speed. In this study the data have been used to derive wave climatology.
- SAR data from both ERS and Radarsat have been used to study winds in coastal areas, wave directional spectra, shallow water bathymetry and to give an indication of surface current patterns and slicks (if visible). These are all of relevance to marine services in the areas.
- Radar scatterometer data is useful for global marine wind monitoring, but its 50 km spatial resolution limits its usefulness for finer-scale coastal applications.

Cloud cover is a major limitation of optical and infra-red satellite data, especially in northern Europe where clouds are present most of the time in coastal regions. The data are most useful for case studies of ocean current structures, sediment transport, and algal blooms. SAR, which is cloud-independent, is limited by the repetition cycles of the satellites, but can be obtained regularly over coastal areas every 3 days. This is not sufficient for operational monitoring. It is expected that the value of SAR data will be improved when data become available every day, and are integrated with other remote sensing data, in situ data, and numerical model studies.

For wind and wave climatology, microwave data from altimeter and scatterometer can provide valuable information, but the data have too coarse a resolution for the coastal zone.

There is a large and diversified need for information in coastal regions, and satellite data has the potential in combination with other data and models to satisfy some of the user requirements. A major limitation in use of satellite data in monitoring coastal waters is insufficient temporal and spatial coverage of existing data. SAR coverage can for example be obtained every 3 days in a given location. The requirement, however, is to obtain new data several times per day in order to have an operational service. In COASTMON, it is therefore of first priority to develop demonstration applications which can become operational in the future, when SAR data are available at least once per day.

C. Brief presentation of the consortium

C.1 NERSC

The Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) was founded in 1986 as an independent non-profit research institute affiliated with the University of Bergen. NERSC performs interdisciplinary basic and applied research related to the physical environment, natural resources and climate by integrated use of satellite and aircraft remote sensing, *in situ* observations, and numerical model tools. The Center plans and executes international research programs funded by research councils, governmental agencies and industry mainly focused on:

- development and validation of remote sensing methods in earth observation,
- applications of remote sensing in coastal management, marine monitoring and forecasting of ocean current, sea ice, and pollution,
- development of numerical models for studies of marine environmental parameters and global /regional climate variations,
- development of assimilation techniques for utilization of remote sensing data in ocean and water quality modeling,
- climate studies with focus on the role of sea ice and ocean circulation at high latitudes,
- CO₂ uptake in the ocean,
- vegetation classification and change detection,
- teaching and training.

A common strategy of the research development of NERSC is based on an integrated approach using information from various sources and combine these with numerical model simulations. This implies that most earth observation development and application studies involves combined use of satellite earth observation data, *in situ* field observation as well as a numerical model component where applicable. NERSC has a close cooperation with a wide range of potential user communities of satellite earth observation data and is member of several scientific user fora and informal groups.

C.2 ARGOSS

Remote sensing technologies contribute efficient and affordable means of collecting environmental data. ARGOSS, established in 1995, is at the leading edge of commercial coastal and offshore remote sensing in Europe. ARGOSS's mission is to bridge the gap between research and the market. ARGOSS has the experience that is required to understand and deliver users need. Cooperation with research institutes and universities helps ARGOSS to focus research and utilize the results in developing new applications. Our staff of 10 includes experts in combining observational data and models to obtain higher-level information, making use of new developments in the geosciences, remote sensing, data-processing and telematics. Most of our specialists have over ten years of experience in R&D and consultancy projects for government and industry.

ARGOSS provides:

- information about the coastal and ocean environment: seabed topography, wind and wave climate, water quality etc.
- R&D services: we develop concepts, techniques and software to utilize measurement data for various purposes, such as bathymetric surveying, measurement of ocean waves and wave climate analysis, flood hazard assessment, MetOcean forecasting
- advice and support: e.g. climate assessment, risk analysis, market surveys, policy and strategy.

C.3 DNMI

The Norwegian Meteorological Institute (DNMI) was founded in 1866. Today DNMI has approximately 500 employees. The main office is in Oslo, there are regional offices in Tromsø and Bergen. DNMI is responsible for the public weather services in Norway, but provides also special services paid by the users.

DNMI has more than 75 years experience in marine weather forecasting and more than 30 years experience in ocean wave forecasting. During the last 10-20 years DNMI has also forecasted storm surge, ocean currents and oil drift. The increasing offshore oil activity has given new demands to content and quality of the forecasts. To meet these demands DNMI - Marine Forecasting Centre in Bergen was established in 1996. The centre employs 20 meteorologists and provides 24 hours service.

DNMI is responsible for approximately 200 observing stations on land and offshore. Observations are taken up to 8 times daily in accordance with procedures specified by WMO (World Meteorological Organisation). Marine weather observations also include sea state. In addition DNMI has more frequent access (every 10-20 minutes) to observations from some oil platforms with weather observations and wave observations from buoys and wave radars. DNMI is connected to the Global Telecommunication System (GTS) which provides members of WMO with real time global weather observations. DNMI has a receiving station for satellite images (Meteosat and NOAA satellites) in Oslo. Some satellite data are also received on GTS.

DNMI is running operationally numerical models: The HIRLAM atmospheric model, the ECOM3D three dimensional ocean model for water level, currents and ocean temperature,

and the WAM model for waves. These models are regional and are run up to 48 hours. In addition DNMI has access to global atmospheric and wave prognoses up to 10 days from ECMWF (European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts).

DNMI will continue the research and development to improve the methods of weather and ocean monitoring and forecasting. A better use of both ground observations and satellite data in combination with improved high resolution numerical models is of particular importance. Therefore participation in projects like COASTMON and EuroROSE is important for DNMI.

C.4 CRC-UCC

A major area of strength within University College Cork is its research and teaching directed towards coastal zone management. These activities take place across a spectrum of departments including archaeology, civil and environmental engineering, geology, geography and zoology. For over 20 years UCC has been involved in research on marine ecology and maritime engineering. Staff within the departments of Zoology and Geography have extensive experience of ecological monitoring of marine habitats and the application of remote sensing and GIS to habitat monitoring. Staff have particular experience in research on the biodiversity of coastal catchments, vegetation mapping of coastal habitats and ecological studies of estuarine and marine lagoons and inter-tidal rocky shores.

The Coastal Resources Centre is part of the Coastal Zone Institute within UCC, which also incorporates the Hydraulics and Maritime Research Centre and the Aquaculture Development Centre. A primary aim of the Coastal Resources Centre is to investigate the interactions between biological and physical resources and human populations, with a view to establishing sustainable development, and thereafter, stimulating the adoption of scientifically based integrated coastal zone management plans.

The CRC, in connection with the Geography Department, has developed extensive expertise in applications of GIS to the coastal zone. Since 1987 the Geography Department has developed the best equipped GIS laboratory in the third level sector in Ireland. Since then the staff have been involved in the following initiatives: co-operation with the United Nations Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR) in the development of training materials for, and presentation of workshops on GIS and Coastal Zone Management; an investigation and documentation of the application of GIS and related technologies to the coastal zone, under the auspices of the International Geographical Union's Commission of Coastal Systems; the development of a Coastal GIS as part of an EU funded project called IMPACTS; host to CoastGIS 95, the first international symposium on GIS and computer mapping for Coastal Zone Management (February 1995) attended by over 100 GIS experts from around the world; organiser and host to an EU MAST Advanced Study Course "Geographic Information Systems (GIS) Applications to Coastal Science and Engineering, September 1995.

II. WORK ACHIEVED

A. Overview

Several satellite systems can provide useful metocean data such as altimeter, scatterometer and passive microwave radiometers. All these systems provide relatively coarse resolution data, which are most useful for monitoring large ocean areas. For the coastal waters, higher resolution is needed and only SAR systems can provide data independent of weather and light conditions.

The SAR has potential to monitor features such as surface wind, wave and current fields, surface slicks including oil pollution, bathymetry and coastal morphology. However, a major part of the information content of SAR images is qualitative — for instance, it is able to localise eddy and frontal features, but algorithms are not yet available to derive current speeds or gradients from SAR data — and have to be combined with other data or numerical model results in order to generate products which satisfy certain quantitative user requirements. Hence, it is foreseen that for most coastal applications, SAR data will have to be integrated into an information system comprising other satellite and *in situ* data as well as model results. The work in this project were organized in the following four work packages:

- WP1: Identify gaps between current monitoring technology and user requirements.
- WP2: Improvements of available products
- WP3: User demonstrations
- WP4: User assessment, conclusions and recommendations

Potential user groups have been involved in all phases of the project and an iterative process based on user feedback pursued in developing relevant products and services. The progress and results for each work package are described below.

B. Results

WP1: Identify gaps between current monitoring technology and user requirements

A user requirement study was performed in three regions: Norwegian, Dutch and Irish coastal regions. The methodology was to use established contacts with the main users of marine and coastal data and arrange dedicated user workshops in each of the three countries. The most important user categories are: weather forecasting services, coastal and harbour authorities with responsibilities for ship traffic, coastal management, etc., pollution authorities, fisheries and aquaculture, offshore industry, navy and coast guard, marine research and resources management, shipping and ferry companies, energy companies, coastal engineering firms, local government and planning authorities, leisure activities and education.

Remote sensing techniques have, over the last two decades or so, been developed to the stage that reliable information products of ocean wind, waves, sea surface temperature, ice conditions, eddy and frontal location and propagation as well as water quality parameters can be produced

Table 1: Sea surface features and processes observed by remote sensing techniques. X: cloud-free and/or daylight dependant, #: cloud and daylight independent.

	Remote Sensing technique					
	Visible Near IR	Thermal IR	Passive Microw.	SAR	Radar Altimeter	Scatter- ometer
I Geophysical Variables & Features						
Temperature Fronts		X				
Current Fronts	X			#	#	
Meso-scale eddies	X	X		#	#	
Upwelling	X	X		#		
Wind Fronts				#		
Wind Speed			#	#	#	#
Wind Direction				#		#
Surface Waves				#	#	
Internal Waves				#		
II Water Quality						
Algae Blooms	X					
Surfactants	X			#		
Oil Spill	X	X		#		
Turbidity/Sediments	X					
III Sea Ice						
Ice Concentration	X		#	#		
Ice Types			#	#		#
Ice Motion	X			#		
Ice Edge	X	X	#	#	#	#

routinely from various earth observation (EO) sensors [Ikeda and Dobson, 1995]. So far the most frequent variables retrieved from satellite sensors used in national and international pre-operational or operational applications are related to wind, waves, temperature and sea ice conditions. Table 1 gives a summary of the main geophysical features and processes that can be observed with different satellite remote sensing sensor systems and processing tools available today. Using remote sensing EO data it is important to consider that satellites observe only the ocean surface. In order to achieve three-dimensional marine information and forecasts, remote sensing data together with in-situ data must be assimilated in numerical models. Hence an integrated approach is essential in order to take advantage of the information embodied in satellite EO data for the ocean and coastal regions.

Large-, regional- and meso-scale weather and ocean features in the European waters can be monitored by polar orbiting EO satellites with sensors operating in a wide range of the electromagnetic spectrum. Passive or active microwave sensors acquire data independent of daylight and clouds, ideal for high latitude observations of sea ice and climate change monitoring, but are also used to monitor wind, waves, ocean currents and oil spills. Visual and infra-red (IR) sensors monitor sea surface temperature, fronts, currents, eddies and ocean color. Small-scale features such as local pollution and floods can be monitored with polar orbiting radar and high-resolution visual satellite sensors.

User requirements in Norway

The Weather service

Scatterometer data (large scale) and SAR data (local scale) available in real time can contribute to better estimates of surface winds, SAR wave spectra can contribute as input data to wave forecasting models, and altimeter data are useful for significant wave height measurements.

Fedje Ship Traffic Control Centre

All information about wind, waves, currents, fronts, eddies and marine pollution in the area of responsibility for the Fedje Centre is needed. It is particularly important to obtain data with sufficient resolution near the coast, in the fjords and straits where much of the ship traffic is concentrated. It is assumed that SAR, available in real time, data can contribute to provide such high resolution information.

Pollution authority

The State Pollution Control Authority is using SAR data from ERS for operational monitoring of oil spills in Norwegian waters, in combination with aircraft surveys. It is required to have more frequently observations and better spatial coverage of SAR.

Fisheries and aquaculture

Satellite data is not used directly, but improved weather and wave forecasts is needed from DNMI. NOAA AVHRR satellite data have been demonstrated as useful tool in combination with in situ observations and models in cases of toxic algae blooms. SAR data can be used to monitor fishing vessels and SeaWiFS data can improve monitoring of chlorophyll for fishery management. Altimeter, scatterometer and SAR data can be used to improve climatic estimates of winds, waves and frontal locations.

Offshore industry

For offshore production such as in the North Sea reliable forecasts of weather and waves are essential. All data, including satellite data, which contribute to better forecasts are useful. During specific operations, such as towing of large platforms, there is need for special monitoring and forecasting of the environmental conditions. For drilling in deeper waters, with floating constructions, it is important to have better knowledge about currents at different depths. This requires better modelling and observations. Both altimeter and SAR can contribute to better data on currents, fronts and eddy statistics.

Navy and Coast Guard

The Navy and Coast Guard vessels need improved real time information received onboard. All types information is useful: wind, waves, currents, eddies, fronts, internal waves, pollution, ship detection, etc. SAR data will be of primary importance, both as support data during daily operations and for general oceanographic knowledge.

Table 2 summarizes the information requirements for the main users in Norway, and the Fedje VTS centre requirements are detailed in Table 3.

Table 2: Summary of information requirements for the main users in Norway.

User	Activity	Requirements	Products
DNMI, Western Norway	Weather service	Surface wind Wave spectra Significant wave height	Scatterometer and SAR derived wind SAR wave spectra Altimeter
Fedje VTS Centre	Coastal authority	Wave, current and pollution data	SAR wave spectra, SAR wind fields, eddy and frontal maps combining SAR and other data, surface current fields from altimeter and models
State Pollution Control Authority	Pollution Authority	Location of pollution events	SAR data showing potential oil spills
Fishery Directorate	Fisheries and aquaculture	Environmental statistics and location of fishing vessels	SAR ship location maps Statistics: wave climatology, frontal maps, SST, currents
Individual fishing vessels		Weather and wave forecast	Ocean front maps, wave spectra
Fish farmers		No environmental information is used except in specific situations of extreme temperature, algal blooms, etc.	Ocean fronts maps, SST
STATOIL, SHELL, etc.	Offshore industry	Drilling and production in deep waters with floating constructions required better information about currents and eddies	Surface current from altimeter, ocean frontal maps from SAR and AVHRR
Navy vessels and marine headquarters	Navy and Coast Guard	Location of fishing vessels, currents, eddies, fronts, temperature, sound velocity, general monitoring of oceanographic conditions	SST maps, ocean frontal maps from SAR and AVHRR, currents from altimeter

Table 3: Requirements from a specific user: the Fedje VTS Centre.

Required product	Current status	Data and model input
Surface current	Not available from satellite data in the near-coastal region. Altimeter data provides barotropic currents in open ocean. High resolution ocean models, combined with SAR for localization of fronts and eddies, can be useful. Ocean Surface Current Radar mounted on land, also in combination with SAR, seems to be the most promising remote sensing technique	Wind fields from models Current fields from models Surface slope from altimeter SAR images
Eddies and fronts	SAR in combination with AVHRR can be used to map the location and propagation of eddies and fronts, but do not provide quantitative velocities. Ocean models can simulate eddies and fronts if they have sufficient resolution and relevant input data. Operational ocean models with typical 50 km resolution do not resolve eddies and fronts	SAR and AVHRR data High-resolution ocean models
Wave height	Available from altimeter data, but not near land and with poor resolution in open ocean. Available from wave models. SAR wave spectra can be used as input to the models	Wave models Altimeter SAR data: input to models
Wave length and direction	Wave models provide the whole spectrum, SAR can give the longer waves (i.e. above 50 - 100 m). SAR provide high spatial resolution and information in fjords, straits and near the coast.	SAR images Wave models
Wave period	Wave models provide the whole spectrum. SAR can give input to the models.	Wave models SAR data: input to models
Surface wind velocity	Can be obtained from scatterometer (coarse resolution, i.e. 50 - 100 km) and from SAR (fine resolution i.e. 5 - 10 km). Wind speed can also be obtained from altimeter. Atmospheric models provides wind fields at resolution of typically 50 km, depending on model resolution.	Scatterometer SAR altimeter models
Ship detection	Location of ships outside the radar range would be useful if available in real time	SAR
Oil spill detection	Identification of oil spills in real time will be useful, especially if the information can be used to proved which ships have cause the pollution	SAR
Other environmental parameters: SST, water colour, etc.	With increasing responsibility for environmental monitoring the Fedje Centre would need information about temperature, chlorophyll and other ocean colour information as supplement to current and wave data.	AVHRR/ATSR SeaWiFS

User requirements in the Netherlands

Ship traffic management

The most important requirement is to improve the bathymetry charting, providing frequently updates of the charts. In addition is important to get high resolution wind fields to improve the wave and water level models which are used in the design of dikes and other flood protection structures. Real time data is needed to improve the monitoring and forecasts of wind, waves, swell, visibility, SST and sediment transport. Satellite data of various kind (SAR, AVHRR, SeaWiFS) can provide input data to such operational service.

Oil industry

For exploration and exploitation of oil and gas on continental shelves, and the edges of these shelves, oil companies need data on wind, waves, swell and currents. Statistical data are needed for design purposes, while real-time data and forecasts are required during operations. Important data sources are altimeter data from all previous and existing satellites, scatterometer data and SAR data.

Energy companies

There are many concepts for extraction of energy from the ocean. The most important technologies use surface waves, and climate data on waves is essential for planning of the energy production plants. Altimeter wave statistics is useful, but the spatial resolution is too coarse. High resolution wave climatology from SAR would be very useful near the coasts to find the best locations for the plants.

Rijkswaterstaat

The national authority for coastal and water management (Rijkswaterstaat) need all types of information about bathymetry (sand banks) and water quality (temperature, concentration of suspended matter and chlorophyll) along the Dutch coast. Bathymetric charts from SAR data are important, and so are the water quality data from spectrometer data on SeaWiFS. An important requirement is to improve the resolution of the spectrometer data in order to monitor the near coastal region.

Heeremac

Heeremac is a major company involved in oil drilling, deployment of offshore pipelines and other marine operations. The company needs good quality wave climatology for all the continental shelves around the world where it operates. SAR derived wave information would be useful, but it necessary to collect SAR data of the specific locations for years to get enough data for the statistical estimates of wave parameters.

The key Netherlands users and their requirements are found in Table 4.

User requirements in Ireland

The main users of metocean data in Ireland are

Naval Service

Use of SAR to monitor possible pollution incidents at sea. Real-time access to data is essential. Detection of discharge of ballast water, by temperature difference (high res. IR images) or

Table 4: Summary of key users and requirements for The Netherlands.

User	Activity	Requirements	Products
KNMI Rijkswaterstaat	Ship traffic management Operational forecasts (Approaches to Rotterdam and Antwerp harbours)	Bathymetry, high-resolution wind fields	Wind (scatterometer, cloud tracking) Waves (altimeter), swell (SAR) Visibility (NOAA, MeteoSat) Sediment transport (NOAA, MOS, SeaWIFS)
Shell International	Oil industry. Exploration of (edge of) continental shelves around the world	Distributions of wind speed/direction Sig. wave height, swell period/energy/direction Joint statistics of wave period and energy	Altimeter, scatterometer SAR wave mode (spectral data not available at present) Buoy records at a limited no. of locations Wave models may be poor
Teamwork Technology	Wave power	High-spatial resolution average wave height along coast of Portugal	Altimeter Global wave models too coarse Buoy records for validation Available information needs to be processed appropriately
Rijkswaterstaat	Management of Dutch coastal waters	Water quality: temperature, suspended matter, chlorophyll Bathymetry: regular monitoring	NOAA, SeaWIFS, MOS SAR
Heeremac	Transportation of oil platforms Laying of pipelines Continental shelves around the world	Climatology of wave spectra to calculate vessel motion response	SAR (but spectral data not available at present) Buoy data used if available. Ship measurements too poor Swell from numerical models not adequate

surface roughness difference (SAR images). Use of SAR in long-term studies of coastal erosion and sediment tracking.

Harbour engineers in Cork

Information on sediment flows using optical sensors and SAR for shallow water bathymetry changes.

Coastal engineering firms

Wave climate data: They need to know if SAR data can contribute if collected systematically over time, and how they compare with or can improve the existing altimeter data sets.

Harbour masters and ship operators

Wind and wave height: SAR, combined with met data and weather forecast. Especially the funnel effects of winds within harbours observed by SAR will be of interest to shipping. Vessel detection by SAR would be beneficial for the harbour masters.

Nautical Enterprise Centre

Use SAR in ship detection as part of VTMISS (Vessel Traffic Management Information System). Also swell and wave data from SAR would be useful in VTMISS.

Other important users are fishing vessels, aquaculture companies, shipping and ferry companies, national weather services, local government, educational institutions and leisure activities.

Perceived significant gaps within the data (sets)

Main types of data lacking: in order of importance and relevance to the COASTMON project are:

1. General hydrographic data - primarily coastal bathymetry.
2. Wave data.
3. Sea temperature data (surface and bottom).
4. Tidal streams and ocean current data.

1. Bathymetry

The data most frequently quoted as missing was basic bathymetric data. This became of increasing significance for those working in the inshore zone, as changes in channels and submarine banks can occur over relatively short time intervals i.e. bathymetric surveys for some areas need to be repeated at frequent intervals. Obviously the Harbour Masters are responsible for ensuring vessels have safe passage through their ports and usually carry out echo-sounder surveys on an annual basis (they use this data to determine where and how frequently they should be dredging), although this work is very site specific and not of great benefit to end-users outside the immediate area of interest. Many organizations stated that most bathymetric surveys carried out in Irish waters were by the British Navy, and that much of that was done in the 1800s. This clearly needs urgent updating.

2. Wave data

Many organizations desire wave data (direction, as well as height and period), but reckoned that its acquisition was beyond their financial means. The Department of the Marine and some of the hydrographic surveying companies are the only bodies (from the organizations contacted) who actively record the wave climate around the Irish coast. The latter were often deployed in coastal engineering projects. Some of the Harbour Masters have, or are about to acquire, wave rider buoys in their harbour areas, but these will only be of relevance to very restricted regions e.g. Cork Harbour, inner Bantry Bay etc. At present many end-users use hindcasting techniques to forecast wave height. However, most of these models require calibration, and more importantly validation from real data.

3. Sea temperature data

A better understanding of the temperature structure of our seas (in xy and z planes) would enable more efficient tracking of commercial fish species. The present data base is of limited extent, and significant anomalies are regularly being found by BIM. Closer to the shore, all the aquaculture industries contacted make extensive use of temperature data, and many expressed an interest in a seasonal background temperature data set.

4. Tidal streams and ocean current data

Current data (surface and at depth) were desired by some of the organizations surveyed, primarily to understand nearshore effluent dispersion and sediment transport patterns. Current data were also highlighted as being critical so that the spread of toxic algal blooms could be predicted (they develop offshore initially).

Data desired and modes suggested for acquiring it

Data that were stated as desirable in the future, even if not presently collected or available, generally relates to the reported significant gaps in data sets described above. Surprisingly few organizations realized the potential of remote sensing at this stage, and only a handful thought this a useful data source (and often only thought so when prompted). Of all contacted, only the Department of the Marine (Engineering Department), and Met Eireann were actively using remotely sensed data. The Naval Service (in conjunction with the Air Corps) has the facilities for collecting remotely sensed data, but do not use it to collect operational oceanographic observations.

General improved hydrographic (predominantly bathymetric) data was that which was most frequently desired - much of the preset data are too old (much from the 19th Century) and not of a sufficient spatial resolution - modern navigation systems based on GPS simply out-perform the accuracy of the charts. Ireland is the only coastal European nation not to have its own national Hydrographic Institute.

Wave data, especially that which incorporates direction, is absent from most parts of the coast. As with bathymetry, it would have to be carefully assessed if it were economically viable to systematically measure the wave climate for all Irish waters. BIM desired a spatial wave-height map as a safety measure for mariners. Some of the Harbour Masters plan to install wave-rider buoys to give an indication of swell height - these data would only be of local use and as such are a relatively extravagant deployment of resources.

Summary of user requirement study

The user categories and their requirements for the three study areas can be summarized as follows:

- *Coastal, Port and harbour authorities:* These include the Fedje Ship Traffic Control Centre in Norway, Cork Harbour Commissioners and Bantry Harbour Authorities in Ireland, Rijkswaterstaat (Netherlands), and the port authorities in Rotterdam (Netherlands) and Antwerp (Belgium). They are responsible for safe and efficient navigation within their harbour area. They require data on metocean conditions within and near their areas of responsibility, and satellite radar provides the opportunity for monitoring wind, wave, current, changes in shallow-water bathymetry, and oil spills.
- *Navy, coastguard, and emergency response services:* These institutions require metocean information for their operations and also to calculate the movements of disabled vessels, pollutants and hazardous floating objects, and missing small craft, life-rafts etc. Meocean data obtained by space techniques will be useful for computing such movements.
- *Fisheries and aquaculture:* These activities are sensitive to sea temperature (detectable by satellite infra-red observations) and pollution and other disturbances from harbour observations. Shellfish cultivation in particular requires a very clean environment, so that the fate of both routine and well as accidental pollution releases from harbour activities, and also related industrial and residential activities, is important. Satellite radar can indicate local current patterns which have importance for pollution transport.
- *Oil companies:* Including the companies operating to and from the refineries and terminals at Mongstad, Sture, Kollsnes (Norway) and Rotterdam, and the Irish National Petroleum

Company which is involved in oil transport to and from Bantry Bay. They are interested in metocean conditions, including variations in current and shallow-water bathymetry, as they affect the navigation of VLCCs. They are also interested in assessing the risks from oil spills (visible in SAR) and pollution events at the processing installations.

- *Insurance companies:* These require the assessment of weather damage and pollution risks. Space techniques can monitor the wind and waves over water areas, and can also give an indication of local variations and thus the variation of hazard from place to place.
- *National weather services:* Including the consortium member DNMI (Norway), and KNMI (Netherlands—specifically KNMI Maritime Services). Space observation can assist in monitoring marine wind and waves and local wind variations, particularly in providing operational guidance to shipping traffic, oil companies, offshore contractors etc.), and also in their oil-spill monitoring operations.

DNMI has the responsibility for providing operational services to the Norwegian Fedje VTS station / Mongstad refinery and Kollsnes/Sture oil and gas terminals.

KNMI Maritime Services are responsible for operational guidance to Rotterdam and Antwerp harbours.

- *Local government and planning authorities:* These include Cork Corporation and Cork County Council (Ireland). They have the responsibility for planning industrial developments and resolving multi-user conflicts. The use of space observation techniques for the marine environment (including monitoring radar-observed natural films as an indication of biological processes, in addition to conventional metocean monitoring) integrated with GIS, can be helpful in this task.
- *Shipping and ferry companies:* These users of port facilities will benefit from improved metocean forecasts, and the transporters of oil and hazardous cargoes require impact assessment of the fate of accidental releases.
- *Educational institutions:* These include the Nautical Enterprise Centre Cork Regional Technical College (involved in maritime transport logistics and modelling). Their educational, research, and consultancy activities will benefit from improvements in metocean and coastal zone monitoring techniques which are available from space-based techniques.
- *Leisure activities:* These include local yachting and sailing clubs, who are dependent on wind/wave/current forecasts, and whose activities will be adversely affected by oil spills and pollution events (see above for the applicability of Earth observation techniques).

Based on the user workshops and previous experience and prior contact with users, a summary of products and potential users could be drawn up (Table 5). These are discussed below.

Product 1. High resolution wind field

Algorithms have been developed to extract wind speed from SAR images. These algorithms have been further developed and tested in coastal regions where detailed wind patterns are not resolved with traditional wind models.

Product 2. Wave height - Detection of swell in coastal regions

SAR imagery of a coastal regions offers the unique capability of tracking a swell field as it approaches the coast. By deducting the wave spectrum from the SAR image at different locations

Table 5: Summary of products, data sources and potential users.

Product	Data sources	Potential users
High resolution wind fields	SAR	Coastal, port and harbour authorities. Navy, coastguard, and emergency response services. Oil companies. National weather services.
Wave spectra and other wave parameters	SAR	Ship traffic centers. Weather services. Coastal, port and harbour authorities. Navy, coastguard, and emergency response services.
Wind and wave climatology	altimeter, SAR, scatterometer	Weather services. Offshore industry. Energy companies.
Shallow water bathymetry	SAR	Coastal, port and harbour authorities.
Currents and fronts	SAR	Navy, coastguard, and emergency response services. Offshore industry.
Water quality and oil spills	visual/IR imagery, SAR	Pollution agencies. Navy, coastguard, and emergency response services. Fisheries and aquaculture.

its transformation due to shoaling, refraction and breaking. Detailed information on the dynamics of swell waves in coastal regions is important for morphological studies, and for design of coastal structures. At present, very little quantitative wave information is being derived from SAR imagery. Over the past few years only a small number of algorithms have been developed ([Hasselmann and Hasselmann, 1991], [Krogstad *et al.*, 1994]). These algorithms require a first guess wave spectrum that is usually obtained from a numerical model. As this puts a severe constraint of the applicability of this technique, we intend to develop a method that can work independently from a priori knowledge.

Product 3. Wind and wave climatology

All companies representing industries that perform critical operations at sea are dependent on wave climate information. For the planning of dredging, towing and heavy lifting operations high quality wind and wave climate assessments are highly valued. The companies that were interviewed emphasised that their interest was not limited to the North-West European coastal waters. In fact, they experienced most problems in remote areas where the access to data was limited, such as along the West coast of Africa or in the coastal waters of South East Asia. Another important outcome of the user survey was the need for spectral wave data. Several companies in Europe offer wave climate atlases based on significant wave height measurements obtained from altimeter missions. These data lack wave period and directional information. The only instrument that can offer spectral wave measurements with a global coverage is the ERS-1/2 SAR. Operating in wave mode, this instrument has acquired over 4 million spectral observations since 1991. This unique data set could be used to enhance traditional wave climatologies based on altimeter data. To this end an algorithm needs to be developed and validated that is capable of extracting spectral wave data from SAR measurements. This algorithm then needs to be applied to the ERS SAR wave mode observations. The resulting database has to be made accessible for the maritime industry.

Product 4. Shallow water bathymetry

SAR imagery of coastal regions contains bathymetric information. ARGOS has developed a method, known as the Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS), that is now used operationally by the Dutch coastal authorities to cut back on traditional depth measurements. The BAS system is tuned to be used in combination with depth measurements. A related application could be to enhance the quality of existing, relatively coarse maps. In the COASTMON project a demonstration of such an application will be performed in the Irish coastal water. In one specific region of interest the quality of an existing admiralty chart will be enhanced using ERS-1/2 SAR imagery acquired over the past few years.

Product 5. Currents and fronts

SAR has shown promising capability to map currents and fronts during favourable wind conditions ($< \approx 10$ m/s). No quantitative current speed can be derived, but directions and eddy structures can be mapped. Frontal features can also be obtained from AVHRR (temperature) and optical instruments (water colour).

Product 6. Water quality and oil spills

SAR is used operationally in Norway for oil slick monitoring. Techniques and algorithms for slick classification from SAR is under development.

Satellite data capabilities and limitations

The COASTMON user investigations show that there are many different users who can use information from a few key satellite sensors. SAR is the primary sensor that can provide this information, but altimeter, AVHRR, scatterometer and SeaWiFS are also useful. However, regardless of how good the present and future algorithms are, a fundamental problem for meeting these user requirements are mis-matches between the time-space scales of processes and parameters and those of the various sensor systems. Figure 1 gives an overview of many processes and parameters which are important in the coastal zone as a function of temporal and spatial resolution. The figure also indicates which satellites can provide relevant information, and in what resolution the satellite data can provide data. For processes with temporal resolution of a few days and spatial resolution of 1 km, there are several satellite sensors which can be useful. A severe limitation of many of these sensors is the cloud problem, which makes the effective observation frequency lower than a few days. In northern Europe, cloud cover can prevail for weeks, making data such as AVHRR, SeaWiFS, SPOT and Landsat practically useless for studies of processes which change within a few days such as ocean current structures, flooding and algae blooms.

The SAR instrument, which is cloud-independent, is limited by the repetition cycle of the satellites. During the three day repetition cycles, and during the ERS-1 - ERS-2 tandem operation with 1 day time interval, it has been demonstrated that some processes such as ocean fronts can be monitored. But for many of the processes which the SAR is suitable to observe change much more rapidly than the observation frequency. This is primarily the case for observations of waves, wind, estuarine tides/fronts and ship detection. Therefore, current spaceborne SAR data can be useful supplement to other observations, but for monitoring purposes it is required to have observations several times per day. Geostationary satellites such as METEOSAT has the capability to observe processes almost continuously, but the resolution

Figure 1: Overall illustration of the temporal and spatial scales of a variety of coastal zone parameters and processes, combined with coverage characteristics for relevant satellites and instruments (from [ESA, 1995]).

of METEOSAT is too coarse for coastal zone monitoring.

For wave and wind climatology, it is clear that cloud independent microwave data from altimeter and scatterometer can provide valuable information since the data can be systematically collected over several year. Altimeter and scatterometer data are most relevant for large-scale observation of the oceans. For the coastal zone these instruments have too coarse resolution.

In spite of the many limitations in use of satellite data in the coastal zone, it has been demonstrated that data such as ERS SAR, with resolution of about 25 m has a large potential for observation of many of the most important processes. Wave spectra, oil spill detection, shallow water bathymetry and ship detection are some applications which are performed operationally today. Other processes can clearly be observed by SAR, such as currents, eddies, fronts, flooding, erosion, estuarine tides, to name a few. But these processes also need to be observed by other methods in order to get more extensive information. It is foreseen that SAR data should be used more systematically with other remote sensing data and *in situ* observations, and that the integrated observations should be used with numerical models.

The COASTMON investigations are, of course, neither comprehensive in terms of geographic areas nor in terms of all possible user requirements. However, they are probably reasonably representative such that conclusions may be drawn. In summary, the results of the COASTMON user investigations have shown that there is a large and diversified need for information in coastal regions, and that satellite data has the potential in combination with other data and models to satisfy many of the user requirements. However, these user investigations have also pointed out some clear gaps between the users' need for information and what information is currently available. Some of the gaps cannot be filled, such as the temporal and spatial SAR coverage, simply because of the constraints given by the existing satellite programmes.

WP2: Development of improved EO data products

The aim of WP2 was to develop EO data products which can provide useful information for many different users such as weather forecasting services, coastal and harbour authorities with responsibilities for ship traffic, coastal management, etc., pollution authorities, fisheries and aquaculture, offshore industry, navy and coast guard, marine research and resources management, shipping and ferry companies, energy companies, coastal engineering firms, local government and planning authorities, leisure activities and education.

The main activities have been:

- Development and test of an algorithm for deriving wind speed from SAR images were refined and used in the project, and comparison with modelled wind fields.
- Development of a new algorithm for deriving spectral wave data from SAR image spectra, and adaptation of it for SAR image mode data. Both this new algorithm as well as earlier algorithms were tested in Norwegian and Irish coastal areas and compared with buoy data.
- A planning tool for marine operators and emergency response units was augmented with monthly statistics of wind and waves, which were integrated with a GIS at ARGOSS. Data from this system (CLAMS) were also made available online, through the Internet.
- The GIS based Wave Atlas for Ireland was also further developed in the project, allowing comparison of wave height data obtained from a numerical model (WAM) and remote sensing data (altimeter).
- The Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) was enhanced and integrated with the Cork GIS for demonstrations in Irish waters. The inclusion of auxiliary data from the GIS helped the BAS users determine suitable locations for applying the bathymetry algorithm.
- Mapping of ocean fronts, eddies and current patterns has been demonstrated by SAR. Field observations have been used to document that frontal features in SAR images can be explained by gradients in the surface current field.
- SAR has also been used to observe natural surface slicks and man-made slicks such as oil spills. The wind speed is the main limiting factor, making observations difficult at wind speeds above 10 m/s.
- The Erim Ocean Model (EOM) was amended to take account of wave breaking processes generating extra centimetre-scale waves, but the initial analysis of model results indicated that further development of this model is needed to meet the user requirements.
- During the project period, DNMI used a wave model (WAM) for both high (10 km) and more coarse (50 km) resolution. The work in COASTMON contributed to the development of a data assimilation algorithm for altimeter data in this model. Further development and validation of DNMI's models will continue in other projects, such as EuroRose (MAST-III).

The work has resulted in five main types of products: (1) high resolution wind fields from SAR, (2) spectral wave data from SAR, (3) wind and wave climatology from altimeter, (4) shallow water bathymetric charts, and (5) a group of SAR-derived products which map features such as currents, fronts and oil spills. In addition, the potential benefits of synergetic use of EO techniques in the analysis of selected ocean parameters was investigated, such as sea surface height and circulation features.

SAR is not the only important spaceborne instrument for observation of ocean processes. Therefore, existing algorithms were applied to generate products for algal bloom and sea surface temperature from AVHRR images using IR and optical channels. The main limiting factor for visual/IR data is the cloud cover. Synergetic remote sensing was attempted in a few cases, and the most promising result was for detection of large and meso-scale circulation features using SAR and thermal IR imagery. This combination of satellite data can provide useful complementary information which can be associated with bathymetric features.

Examples of the five types of products are shown in the following sections.

High resolution wind field from SAR

An improved algorithm for derivation of wind speed from SAR images was developed during the COASTMON project. This SAR wind algorithm (SWA) is based on the spectral properties of full-resolution images. The algorithm is based on a relation between the smearing effects in the SAR image and the wind field, and does not require absolute calibration of the radar data [Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998].

The SWA is derived from a comparison of ERS SAR wave-mode data and the ERS wind scatterometer data which can be simultaneously acquired with the same satellite. In the case of a fully developed sea (no fetch limitation), the empirical SWA relation, based on an evaluation of 1200 SAR wave-mode images with a central incidence angle of 20.2 degrees, is given by [Chapron *et al.*, 1995] as

$$U_{10} = 4.75 \left(\frac{\lambda_c - 30}{110} \right) \text{ m s}^{-1},$$

where U_{10} is the wind speed at 10 m above the surface and λ_c is the azimuth cutoff wavelength. The algorithm has also been compared with DNMI winds (Table 6) and with ERS scatterometer winds.

The methods of retrieving high resolution wind fields from SAR images which is illustrated here can be seen as complementary to the conventional wind observations from platforms and buoys. Where the conventional observations give an overview of the development of the wind with time on a limited set of locations, the SAR provides a good spatial overview on a limited number of occasions. In the case of the IJsselmeer (Figure 2), about one SAR image of the ERS satellites (operational since 1991) is available every two weeks. Analysis of in-situ wind measurements in combination with the high resolution SAR wind fields will lead to a better description of the wind climate in near shore regions, and hence to better estimates of the extreme wave heights and storm surges.

Further examples of wind derived from SAR data area shown in Figures 3-4.

Table 6: Table showing comparison between SAR wind and DNMI-wind.

Date	CMOD-4 SAR wind	Atmospheric model prediction
19.Dec.1997	3 m/s (Troll) 3 m/s (Hellesøy)	2.5-5.0 m/s SE
04.Jan.1998	10 m/s (Troll) 13 m/s (Hellesøy)	13.0 m/s S

Figure 2: Wind speed analysis for ERS SAR images

Top left: IJsselmeer, 1995 Feb 6. Top right: Waddenzee, 1994 May 13

Middle left: Waddenzee, 1994 May 13. Middle right: Dutch coast, 1995 June 23

Bottom left: Dutch coast, 1995 July 2. Bottom right: Dutch coast, 1995 July 9

Figure 3: Wind field in the Greenland Sea measured by the ERS-1 WSC on September 1, 1995. Sea level pressure given by the Hindcast database of the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (DNMI). The frames indicate the position of SAR scenes available from this day.

Figure 4: ERS-2 SAR image covering the atmospheric front on September 1, 1995, with the WSC wind field overlaid. The white box is framing a sub-image of 25x25 km. The horizontal dark band is an artifact.

Using high resolution ERS SAR data, wind fields can be derived on scales down to a few hundred meters. The algorithm has been tested in Norwegian coastal waters for wind speeds between 5 m/s and 14 m/s, and the accuracy of the algorithm varied between $\pm 1-2$ m/s and up to $\pm 5-6$ m/s by comparing with in situ wind measurements [Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998].

Users of high resolution wind fields such as meteorological institutes, ship traffic managers and harbour authorities, Navy and Coast Guard vessels and offshore industry, all require frequent and regular data, typically 2-4 times per day, to support their operational work. This cannot be satisfied with today's satellites, where a typical revisit period is 3 days. Hence, more satellites are needed to meet the need for more frequent data. The advantage of SAR-derived wind is the high-resolution wind fields which are more detailed and accurate than the standard meteorological wind products. The SAR images can provide wind fields gridded to a few km. The altimeter on the other hand, cannot provide such detailed data about local wind conditions, and is not well suited for users in ship traffic management or route planning. The offshore industry, such as oil companies, are also interested in statistical data, i.e. wind climate data, and such data requirements are more likely to be met by the currently available satellites.

Wave data products

Significant wave height can be derived from satellite altimeter data, for use in operational wave forecasting [Breivik *et al.*, 1998]. The resolution of the wave height estimates from altimeter along the track is about 7 km. The wave field is a gridded data set developed by a wave model using altimeter as one of the input data.

During the COASTMON demonstration period (December 1997 - February 1998), a land based radar was placed near Fedje VTS Center, and from these measurements directive wave spectra were estimated. Such spectra can also be estimated by a wave model (WINCH) and from ERS SAR data. A comparison between the resulting spectra from the different sources was made, and showed that the wave model estimates were in good agreement with the measured data, while the spectra derived from only SAR data were less accurate. The best results are obtained when satellite data are used in combination with modelling.

Coastal surveyance and engineering activities require a high spatial resolution, which is best met by derivation of wave spectra from SAR data. Other users, such as meteorological institutes, are also interested in detailed data for generating high resolution forecasts in e.g. the coastal zone.

The main limiting factor for generation of high resolution wave products are the lack of daily (or better) coverage with the satellites available today. Obtaining data from a land based radar may be an alternative for organisations needing information about a small area, but is not practical for surveyance of larger areas extending several hundred km from the coast.

Significant wave height is available from satellite altimeter data and this is used in wave forecasts by DNMI [Breivik and Reistad, 1992]. An example of significant wave height forecast for the North Atlantic and Norwegian Sea is shown in Figure 5.

Information on the directional wave spectrum can be obtained from SAR images, by an inversion technique which normally uses a 'first guess' wave spectrum, based, for example, on the wind-wave spectrum associated with the local wind field obtained from model results. Such methods have been described in e.g. [Hasselmann and Hasselmann, 1991] and

[Krogstad, 1992, Krogstad *et al.*, 1994].

To investigate the capability of the SAR to image waves propagating into harbour areas, it is difficult to use a wave model. For each area that is to be analysed, a wave model has to be set up, and for each image a wave model runs needs to be executed. This would make this method too expensive to be of any practical use. Hence a retrieval algorithm is needed that is capable of interpreting a SAR image spectrum without any a priori knowledge about the sea state.

In Figure 6 a SAR spectrum is shown that was observed by the ERS-1 on January 30, 1993, 11:36 GMT at 28W, 42S. According to the model a wind of 14 m/s is blowing along the range axis, according to the scatterometer it is a few m/s stronger and turned towards the negative azimuth axis. Also shown in Fig. 5 are the SAR spectra of the wave spectra retrieved with both methods. Compared to the significant wave height of 3.3 m from the wave model first guess, both schemes show an increase (4.4 and 5.1 m for the Hasselmann *et al* and the new scheme respectively). This example shows that it is possible to retrieve spectral wave information from SAR wave mode spectra without a priori knowledge about the sea state. This means SAR wave mode products of the ERS satellites can be used more easily, as they do not have to be matched with spectra from a numerical wave model to be interpreted. In cases when the wind is strong enough, it is shown to be possible to retrieve the wind direction from the observed SAR spectrum. A comparison with wave spectra retrieved with the [Hasselmann *et al.*, 1996] scheme shows reasonable agreement in most cases. A comparison of both methods with spectral buoy observations is necessary to validate both methods.

In the past year ARGOSS has developed such an algorithm. Rather than a 1st guess wave spectrum, it uses an estimate of the local wind. The method has been validated using the SAR wave mode data set acquired by the ERS-1 and ERS-2 missions. Unlike the data obtained

Figure 5: Significant wave height from the WINCH model, 1998 February 10, 06h UTC (6-hour forecast).

Figure 6: Comparison of wave spectra retrieved with the method of [Hasselmann *et al.*, 1996] (left column) and with the new method (right). In the top row the SAR spectra are shown, with the observed SAR spectrum in the middle. The wave spectra retrieved with both models are shown on the bottom row.

with the SAR in image mode, the data acquired in the wave mode have a global coverage. By collocating the SAR wave mode spectra with buoy records (in particular those measured by the American NOAA buoys) we were able to construct a data set large enough to derive some statistics about the retrieval method. In the scatter plot of Figure 7, the retrieved height of the waves longer than 12 seconds (i.e. wavelength longer than about 225 m) is shown as a function of the height observed by 11 NOAA buoys. The SAR is capable of retrieving the height of these long waves with a 25 % accuracy.

To obtain a collection of ocean wave spectra from a SAR image the following steps are taken:

1. The PRI SAR image product which is used for the present version gives the 3-look normalised radar backscatter amplitude on a grid with a spacing of 12.5 m. In the first step the 100 by 100 km image is divided into 5 by 5 km blocks. After visual inspection of the image a number of these sub-images can be selected for further processing (see Figure 8).
2. Using the procedure described by Laur *et al.* [Laur *et al.*, 1996] the PRI image is recalibrated. This involves compensating for the power loss in the AD converter of the ERS satellites, that can lead to an underestimation of the radar backscatter of up to 6 dB. The normalised radar backscatter over open water is related to the wind speed, wind direction and the incidence angle of the radar.
3. The selected 5 by 5 km sub-images are read from CD-ROM and averaged to a 25 by 25 m resolution. The power spectra of the radar backscatter are stored in an ASCII file

Figure 7: Validation of the ARGOSS SAR wave spectra retrieval algorithm. Shown here is the retrieved height of the waves with periods longer than 12 seconds (225 m).

together with some ancillary data such as the incidence angle and the satellite heading.

4. The SAR image power spectra are transformed to ocean wave spectra by inverting the nonlinear mapping relations proposed in [Hasselmann and Hasselmann, 1991].

An example of a SAR sub-image showing a swell system is shown in Figure 9.

Product examples

The above method has been applied to a SAR image acquired on December 19, 1992, of the Irish south coast (see Figure 8). The image shows swell waves entering from the South. The spectra of the nine selected sub-images are shown in Figure 10. The radar backscatter shows that the wind speed at the time of the image acquisition was low: between 3 and 5 m/s.

Original SAR data © ESA 1992

Figure 8: A SAR image acquired on 19 December 1992 of the South coast of Ireland. The nine selected sub-images are indicated.

Original SAR data © ESA 1992

Figure 9: Sub-image cut out from the SAR image shown in Figure 8. The sub-image corresponds to the spot marked 1 in Figure 8.

Figure 10: The nine SAR image spectra corresponding to the locations marked in Figure 8.

Global wave climate assessment system by SAR

Introduction

One of the outcomes of the Dutch user requirements workshop (held at May 5, 1997 at ARGOSS) was that the Dutch users see the largest potential for remote sensing products in assessing the situation in remote areas. Apart from the bathymetry assessment system, which seems to have a large potential in Dutch coastal waters, most other applications that remote sensing techniques can be put to have viable, conventional alternatives. This includes the assessment of the wind and wave climate from satellite data. The climate data can be derived cheaply and accurately from a buoy network that has been operated in the Southern part of the North Sea over the past decades. However, the offshore consultancy companies indicated that the bulk of their work involves remote coastal areas outside the Dutch coastal waters. In the majority of these areas no climate data is available. It is clear that remote sensing products, with their global coverage, could be very useful here.

In conversations with end users following the workshop it was established that the requirements for metocean climate data fall in different categories:

- Wave height and wind speed at given location and time, for instance to investigate conditions that led to an accident. Now the service exists, it is also used for other purposes, such as the assessment whether the conditions at any given time and place are favorable for the detection of an oil spill with SAR imagery.
- Capability to make on-line wind and wave climate assessments, in particular to assist in the estimation of the expected downtime during an operation. These assessments have to be made in order to establish the financial risks during the tendering phase.
- Tailored wind and wave climate tables for a given location (on paper and digital). For the actual planning of offshore operations, but also to run morphological models, users often prefer to define the exact format of the climate data they want to receive.

It was also indicated that for the latter two products, i.e. the wind and wave climate assessments, spectra wave climate data was essential. The only satellite sensor that can provide these data is the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR). Over the past 6 years, the ERS-1 and ERS-2 satellites have collected an archive of SAR image spectra from which ocean wave spectra can be derived. This dataset has a global coverage, and the density of measurements is sufficient to allow climate estimates. In the scope of COASTMON an algorithm has been developed to retrieve ocean wave climate data from these SAR measurements. This algorithm has been applied to all recorded SAR wave mode observations, and the results have been used to set up both the online climate system CLAMS, and an offline climate service.

Technical description

The way in which an ocean wave spectrum is mapped onto a SAR spectrum is reasonably well understood. Hasselmann and Hasselmann [Hasselmann and Hasselmann, 1991], hereafter referred to as HH91, have derived a closed set of equations, in which the SAR image spectrum is given as an expansion series in the ocean wave spectrum. The reason for this nonlinear

dependence is that the orbital velocities of the waves interfere with the way in which the SAR constructs its resolution in the azimuth direction. To retrieve an ocean wave spectrum from an observed SAR spectrum means that this nonlinear relation has to be inverted.

The standard method to do this inversion is to start with a first guess wave spectrum, usually from a numerical wave model, and to change this spectrum iteratively until its associated SAR spectrum matches the observed SAR spectrum. A retrieval scheme along these lines is described by HH91. *Krogstad et al.* [Krogstad *et al.*, 1994] developed a simplified method that ignores the nonlinearities in the SAR mapping.

The above mentioned retrieval algorithms are not optimally suited for the derivation of spectral wave climate data. First of all, both methods reject a sizable fraction of the observed SAR spectra: *Heimbach et al.* [Heimbach *et al.*, 1998] reports a rejection percentage of 30 % using the HH91 retrieval method, according to *Breivik et al.* [Breivik *et al.*, 1998] the method of *Krogstad et al.* [Krogstad *et al.*, 1994] rejects half of the available SAR observations. It is clear that the rejection of such large portions of data has a detrimental effect on the wave climate statistics to be derived from the observations. A second disadvantage of both methods is their dependence on the presence of a first guess wave spectrum. For the present purpose, a global wave climate atlas, this is impractical: to generate all necessary wave spectra would require running a global wave model for the whole 6 year period since 1991.

The method developed in the COASTMON project does not require *a priori* knowledge of the sea state to retrieve an ocean wave spectrum for a SAR observation. Instead, the fact that on the ERS satellites the scatterometer is operated simultaneously with the SAR wave mode is exploited. As the SAR measurement is located inside the scatterometer swath, each SAR wave mode spectrum can be associated with a wind vector from the scatterometer. Using a standard parameterization, a first guess wave spectrum is constructed. The stage of development and the exact propagation direction of the wind sea are found by minimizing the difference between the SAR spectrum calculated from the wind sea and the observed SAR spectrum. The residual signal in the observed SAR spectrum is interpreted as swell, and is translated from the SAR spectral domain into the wave spectral domain assuming the mapping relations for these long waves are linear. A more detailed account of the retrieval algorithm is given in Mastenbroek and De Valk [Mastenbroek and de Valk, 1998].

In Figure 11 the relative quality of the retrieved spectra in different frequency bands is compared. The energy in the shortest wave components, with wave periods between 10 and 13 seconds, is slightly underestimated. This may be caused by the azimuth cutoff, which obviously has its largest effect on the shortest wave components. The performance of the system is optimal for waves with a period between 13 and 16 seconds. The relative error in the retrieval of the height of these waves is 32 %, the standard deviation is 0.32 m. For waves with periods longer than 16 seconds the standard deviation is even smaller, 0.26 m, but given the limited amount of energy in this frequency band, the relative performance is worse (44 %).

The above method has been compared to the one described by HH91 for 142 spectra acquired by the ERS-1 on January 30, 1993. No independent in situ data are available for these cases. The retrieved wave heights show good agreement. However, this is not the case for the underlying two dimensional spectra. This is illustrated by examples shown in the Figures 12.

Figure 12 shows a case where a 10 m/s wind is blowing in the negative azimuth direction. In the WAM model the associated wind sea peak has a peak wave length of 30 m (see Figure 1 in [Hasselmann *et al.*, 1996]), which falls outside the domain shown in figure 12. The SAR spec-

Figure 11: Retrieval of the height of the waves in three different frequency bands: (a) wave period between 10 and 13 seconds (length between 150 and 250 m); (b) wave period between 13 and 16 seconds (length between 250 and 400 m) and (c) waves with periods longer than 16 seconds (400 m in deep water).

trum observed by the ERS-1 is very noisy, the signal to noise ratio is only 2.6, and the energy is distributed along the range axis in a slightly skewed way. This spectrum is interpreted completely differently by both schemes. The MPI algorithm matches the observed SAR spectrum by redistributing energy between three different swell systems, whereas the SPRA method concludes there are no swell present at all. The latter scheme explains the low wavenumber signal in the observed SAR spectrum as the nonlinear bands caused by a fully developed, azimuth traveling wind sea. This option is not available to the MPI scheme, as it uses a quasilinear approximation to calculate which changes to the wave spectrum would improve the match with the observed SAR spectrum. Which of the two schemes produced the wave spectrum closest to reality is not known, as no in situ data are available.

Product examples

To meet the demands of end users for up-to-date wind and wave climate information the online service CLAMS (<http://clams.argoss.nl>) has been set up. On this interactive web site, users can select their region of interest by the click of a mouse button. The CLAMS system subsequently gathers all satellite data recorded in that region over the years from a database. The user interface of CLAMS allows users to explore this data set in a number of ways. One option is to select a date of interest, and to plot a timeseries of the wind speed or significant wave height in the area. It is also possible to assess the climatic conditions in the area of interest: for instance the seasonal variation of either the wind speed or the wave height. Other options include the assessment of the different one-dimensional (Figure 13) and two-dimensional (Figure 14) distributions.

Not all users have expressed interest in using the Internet to get wind and wave climate data. Some because they want the climate tables in a format that can be imported in a spreadsheet, some because they are not familiar with the Internet. To satisfy these customers, an offline wind and wave climate service is being set up. The products that are made with this service largely comply with the ones in the CLAMS system. However, the fact that the service is offline

Figure 12: Comparison with the retrieval algorithm developed by the Max Planck Institute (MPI) in Hamburg for a SAR spectrum acquired on January 30, 1993 at 11:38Z in the South Atlantic near the islands of South Georgia (51S, 32W). First column: first guess from the wave model WAM; second column: spectra retrieved with MPI scheme; third column: observed SAR spectrum and wind vector; fourth column: spectra retrieved with the SPRA scheme.

allows for certain refinements that are impossible to implement in an online system. One of these includes the removal of the 180° ambiguity in the propagation direction of the swell. If the region of interest is sheltered by the nearby presence of land, it is often possible to resolve the ambiguity problem by simply assuming that the swell originated from the open ocean.

A few examples of offline wind and wave climate tables are shown in Table 7 and Table 8. The region of interest is the Bay of Khambhat along the North-Western coast of India. The presented tables show the conditions averaged over a year, based on 6 years of observations (1991-1997). Often the tables are also provided per month or per season.

Figure 13: Directional distribution of wave energy from SAR as visualized by the CLAMS system.

height of swell (m) in rows versus period of swell (s) in columns

	< 09	09 .10	10 .11	11 .12	12 .13	13 .14	14 .15	15 .16	16 .17	> 17
< 0.25	50	30	46	43	17	3	2	1	1	0
0.25 - 0.50	3	18	68	105	105	55	18	13	3	0
0.50 - 0.75	0	10	25	56	91	72	34	19	6	0
0.75 - 1.00	0	6	11	23	27	29	26	12	4	2
1.00 - 1.25	0	6	16	10	3	5	5	1	2	3
1.25 - 1.50	0	1	25	11	3	4	0	2	1	1
1.50 - 1.75	0	1	38	15	6	2	1	0	0	0
1.75 - 2.00	0	0	27	43	6	3	1	1	0	0
2.00 - 2.25	0	0	15	42	7	0	0	0	0	0
2.25 - 2.50	0	0	2	42	8	1	0	0	0	0
2.50 - 2.75	0	0	1	21	10	1	1	0	0	0
2.75 - 3.00	0	0	0	17	16	1	0	0	0	0
3.00 - 3.25	0	0	0	4	8	1	0	0	0	0
3.25 - 3.50	0	0	0	1	6	1	0	0	0	0
3.50 - 3.75	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
3.75 - 4.00	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
> 4.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 14: Example of energy distribution of swell as function of wave height (rows) and period (columns) offered by CLAMS.

Table 7: Percentage per significant wave height/wind speed class. Period = all year, N = 46962.

speed [m/s] →	0-2	2-4	4-6	6-8	8-10	10-12	12-14	14-16	16-18	18-20	20-22	22-24
0.00	0.3	1.0	3.5	2.2	1.1	0.5	0.4	0.0				
0.50	0.9	2.9	9.1	6.1	2.8	1.4	6.5	0.1	0.0			
1.00	0.8	2.4	7.6	5.1	2.3	1.0	5.9	0.0	0.0	0.0		
1.50	0.4	1.0	3.4	2.3	1.1	0.5	2.4	0.0	0.0	0.0		
2.00	0.1	0.5	1.6	0.9	0.5	0.2	0.8					
2.50	0.2	0.8	2.4	1.7	0.8	0.3	1.2		0.0	0.0		
3.00	0.1	0.6	1.5	1.1	0.6	0.3	1.2	0.0	0.0			
3.50	0.1	0.5	1.3	0.8	0.4	0.2	0.9	0.0				
4.00	0.1	0.3	0.8	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.5	0.0				
4.50	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0				
5.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0					
5.50	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0								
6.00			0.0									

Table 8: Percentage of time per wind speed/direction class. Period = all year, N =37999.

direction →	0°-30°	30°-60°	60°-90°	90°-120°	120°-150°	150°-180°	180°-210°	210°-240°	240°-270°	270°-300°	300°-330°	330°-360°
0.0	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.29	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.30	0.3	0.4
2.0	2.1	0.8	0.5	0.16	0.21	0.17	0.13	0.4	2.4	2.6	1.4	1.8
4.0	6	1.6	0.8	0.28	0.10	0.05	0.14	1.1	8	10	6	5
6.0	4	1.5	0.4	0.27	0.12	0.03	0.09	1.9	6	5	4	2.6
8.0	1.8	0.4	0.10	0.11	0.07	0.15	0.05	2.6	5	1.0	0.5	0.3
10.0	0.3	0.14	0.02	0.02	0.07	0.19	0.01	1.9	2.6	0.3	0.02	0.02
12.0	0.05	0.02				0.03	0.00	0.5	0.5	0.02	0.01	
14.0								0.02	0.16			
16.0								0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01
18.0									0.02		0.01	0.01

Wind and wave climatology from altimeter data

To meet the needs of marine operational planners and emergency response units, a wave climate data system based on altimeter data was further developed and customised for the Irish application sites. This system, named CLAMS, was extended to show monthly statistics and these data were integrated in a GIS, for use in conjunction with other oceanographic and meteorological data. The products provided by CLAMS are used as a valuable tool for planning marine operations.

The radar altimeter provides good coverage for generation of large scale climatological data and routines for extracting such information for a specific area can be set up. Examples of such products are monthly mean significant wave height and wind speeds for the coast of Ireland.

A wave climate data system, based on radar altimeter data, denoted CLAMS, has been developed at ARGOSS¹. In the COASTMON project we have developed upon this system by aggregating the data into monthly mean, 10% exceedence and 90% exceedence values and integrating the data into a Geographical Information System (GIS). This product allows the user to browse the monthly wave climate spatial trends for the study area spanning between Ireland and Norway (Figure 15). The monthly data can be visualised in 2D, in 3D or as contours. The user can view a bar chart depicting the annual significant wave height or wind speed trends for any user-defined location. In addition the product incorporates an operational planning tool which identifies, over any selected time frame, areas which fall within user-defined limits of significant wave height and wind speed. We anticipate that this product will be of interest to marine operational planners for identifying windows of opportunity and to emergency response units to assist in the strategic planning of resource allocation.

Technical Description

The product is based on radar altimeter data providing significant wave height, H_s , derived from ERS-1, ERS-2 and Topex/Poseidon. In total 10 million measurements were used from the following periods:

¹<http://clams.argoss.nl>

Figure 15: This image depicts the mean significant wave height values for December. This data is available for both significant wave and wind speed for each month in mean, 90% exceedence and 10% exceedence form.

ERS-1 Aug91-May96;
ERS-2 Jun95-Oct97;
T/P Oct92-Dec97

Significant wave height is calculated within a 0.5 degree grid, which spans 18W to 30E Longitude and 48N to 80N Latitude. The data were aggregated into monthly mean, 10% exceedence (10% of the values are below these values) and 90% exceedence (90% of the values are below these values). These data were output as Band Sequential Multiband (BSQ) images. They were imported into ArcView GIS. Since ArcView can only read positive integer values in BSQ format, the BSQ file values were multiplied by 100 to cater for decimal values. In ArcView the BSQ files were converted to a GRID format, a raster format native to, and therefore more flexibly handled by, the GIS. The grids were geo-referenced and projected into UTM to facilitate integration with the other datasets in the Cork COASTMON GIS.

The interface has been customised to allow easy browsing of the 6 datasets (Significant Wave Height monthly mean (h_s), 10% exceedence, 90% exceedence and Wind Speed (W_s) monthly mean, 10% exceedence and 90% exceedence). The datasets can be viewed as 0.5 degree grids or viewed in 3D with the height value representing the H_s or the W_s values, as shown in Figure 16, where the colour coding in this image represents the January wave height 90% exceedence data, however, the z axis represents the wind speed 90% exceedence values for the same months. This correlation of the two datasets facilitates spatial pattern analysis. Interpolated contour data can also be viewed (Figure 17). A visualisation tool has been developed which allows the user to view the temporal change for a user-selected 0.5 degree grid cell (Figure 18). The values are displayed for the selected months via a bar chart.

An operation planning tool has been developed which allows the user to integrate the significant wave height data with the wind speed data to help identify areas and periods suitable for weather sensitive maritime operations (Figure 19). The user is prompted for whether they want to base the analysis on the mean, the 10% exceedence or the 90% exceedence datasets. They are then prompted to select the month(s) of interest. They then enter the maximum Significant Wave Height and Wind Speed values allowable for the planned operation. Finally they identify the boundary of the area they are interested in. The tool returns a grid identifying suitable areas for the operation during that period.

Product examples

Figures 15–19 show examples of the output given by the visualization and operational planning tool.

Shallow water bathymetric charts

The Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) has been developed to enable users to obtain detailed bathymetric maps of coastal regions by means of SAR data and without extensive use of in situ measurements. The BAS has been tested for Dutch and Irish coastal areas in this project. The BAS technique is constrained by the following factors: (1) the tidal current must be >0.5 m/s, (2) the wind speed must be ≥ 3 m/s and <10 m/s, and (3) the depth must be ≤ 50 m. These conditions were satisfied for the Rosslare area on the East coast of Ireland, and the technique was successfully applied to a set of SAR images. By comparing with the British

Figure 16: This image demonstrates the versatility in visualising the data that the GIS lends this product. The image represents the January significant wave height 90% exceedance data, with the wave height represented in both the colour coding and in the z axis.

Figure 17: In this image the same significant wave height data is again depicted, however, in this example the data is represented by interpolated contours.

Figure 18: In addition to representing the entire study area on a monthly basis, a tool has been developed to enable the user to view the annual trend for individual 0.5 degree grid squares.

Figure 19: An operational planning tool has been produced which enables the user to identify areas within a user-specified location where the wind speed and significant wave height during a specific temporal period are suitable for undertaking sensitive maritime operations.

Admiralty Charts, it was found that the BAS generated bathymetry was in good accordance with the map generated from field measurements. The BAS technique was also successfully used in Dutch coastal areas, and customers are also interested in applying it in other parts of the world, e.g. in Asia.

Under favorable meteorological and hydrodynamical conditions features of the bottom topography of shallow seas show up on SAR images. The mechanism by which this happens is indirect, as the radar signal itself penetrates the water only a few millimeters. For moderate incidence angles, radar waves are reflected by short water waves on the surface. The presence of these waves is influenced by gradients in the tidal current, which in turn depends on the bottom topography. To describe this effect mathematical models have been developed. Inversion of these models makes it possible to retrieve topographical information from SAR imagery. Bathymetric surveys traditionally rely on *in situ* depth soundings. With the help of information from SAR imagery the number of traditional depth soundings necessary to produce a depth map of a given quality can be cut down significantly, which has obvious economical advantages.

In the COASTMON project the Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) that is being developed by ARGOSS is applied to the coastal area near Rosslare in the South-East corner of Ireland. This area is suffering from a siltation problem and has been closely monitored over the past decades [Cracknell and Huang, 1988] [Huang and Davies, 1991]. An attempt will be made to enhance the coarse bathymetric information taken from digitized Admiralty charts. These charts are based on a combination of historical data, and on more recent information from harbor masters reported to the British Admiralty. For this purpose three ERS-1/2 SAR images of the area have been analyzed. The resulting depth map is compared with recent high resolution depth soundings that was carried out in 1997.

Technical description

The BAS system is being developed at ARGOSS to map the bottom topography of shallow seas from SAR images and a limited number of depth soundings. The method can be employed in situations with strong (tidal) currents (> 0.5 m/s) in combination with fair wind conditions (3 to 10 m/s). BAS requires the initial depth soundings for calibration purposes. The SAR imagery will be used to fill in the gaps between the initial depth soundings in way that is consistent with the information from the SAR image. The system consists of two parts: an imaging model suite to compute a SAR image for a given depth map and tidal information, and an inversion scheme. A simulated radar image is calculated from a first-guess depth map using the forward model. The difference between the observed and simulated image is expressed in terms of a cost function. In an iterative procedure the depth map is adjusted until the difference between the simulated and observed radar image is minimal.

Based on admiralty charts of the region, an initial depth map was constructed (Figure 21). Three ERS-1/2 SAR images were selected that showed bottom features. These images were acquired on 16 April 1993, 5 April 1997 and 14 April 1997. Details of the images showing the region of interest near Rosslare are shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Radar images of the Rosslare area acquired on 16 April 1993 (left), 5 April 1997 (middle) and 14 April 1997 (right). On the top row the depth contours obtained from the admiralty chart are superimposed.

Product examples

The combination of the initial depth map (Figure 21) with the three SAR images in the BAS system resulted in a revised depth map (Figure 22). Comparing the two figures, we see that the SAR imagery has smoothed the depth chart that was based on the interpolation between depth contours from the admiralty chart. The profiles shown in the figures 23 and 24 give a more detailed picture of the effect of the satellite imagery. In particular the second figure shows that the SAR enhances certain bottom features. In the vicinity of $y = 5797$ three wiggles in the depth are detected, that have an estimated amplitude of several meters.

In the region where reference depth soundings are available, the bottom left corner of the image, the SAR imagery show little detail. Consequently the SAR enhanced depth map is not altered in this region.

Figure 21: Color coded depth map based on admiralty chart.

Figure 22: Depths from the admiralty chart enhanced with the SAR imagery.

Figure 23: Depth profile along the horizontal line $y = 5797.5$. The SAR imagery has smoothed the depths based on the admiralty chart, and has shifted the location of the depth maximum slightly.

Figure 24: Depth profile along the column $x = 690$. The most interesting feature introduced by the SAR imagery are the wiggles in the vicinity of $y = 5797$. The first two SAR images in Figure 20 clearly show these features.

Currents, fronts, and water quality

Current model results and comparison using EO

In the Norwegian study area, the effect of ocean currents can be important in the navigation of very large crude-oil carriers (VLCCs) and other large vessels and offshore structures. The open sea adjacent to the Norwegian coast is subject to the influence of the Norwegian coastal current, which generally flows northwards, but in which eddies occur which may cause extreme currents of up to 1.5 m/s. It is thus important to have an indication of the spatial gradients in the current when passing through the straits separating the open waters from the fjords and inshore waters.

The Norwegian Meteorological Institute (DNMI) operates a three-dimensional numerical ocean current model (ECOM3D), with 20 km grid cells, on a routine basis, and an example of the model results during the COASTMON demonstration period is shown in Figure 25. Although the resolution is coarse, it can be clearly seen that the current near the west coast of Norway is distinctly different from that further from the shore.

Figure 25: Current at 10 m depth from the ECOM3D operational model with 20 km resolution, 1998 February 10, 06h UTC (6-hour forecast). The box in the upper left corner of the plot shows the area where the 4 km resolution model is tested.

Figure 26: Current at 10 m depth from the hydrodynamic model with 4 km resolution, 1998 February 10, 00h UTC (forced by analysed meteorological fields). The location of this high resolution model is west of Haltenbanken, as shown in Figure 25.

DNMI's high resolution ocean model, with 4 km grid cells, can simulate more detailed patterns of the current field such as eddies and meanders within a limited area. Example of output from the high-resolution model is shown in Figure 26.

Such eddy features in the current can be seen in satellite optical and infra-red images, but these are restricted by the presence of cloud cover. SAR images, such as the one shown in Figure 27, also show eddying features in considerable detail, under given environmental conditions.

It is not possible to directly determine the current velocity and direction from the observed features, although many details of current structures can be seen in SAR images, and the theory for the radar imaging of these structures, by means of the interaction of waves, currents, and wind, is well developed. However, it was found possible to evaluate the performance of various numerical models which provide 'indicative' results.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1997

Figure 27: 100×100 km ERS-2 SAR image of the West Norwegian coast, 1998 January 15. The outlet of Sognefjord is near the centre of the image. The main feature to be seen is eddying and frontal structures in the Norwegian coastal current.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1995

Figure 28: ERS-2 SAR image from 11h UTC on 1995 September 27 during the COAST WATCH '95 experiment. The acoustic Doppler current profiler current measurements from the ship, which moved from south to north along the track, are shown by the arrows.

During the COASTWATCH '95 experiment conducted in the autumn of 1995 off the southern coast of Norway, SAR ocean features were investigated using ship and buoy observations of oceanographic and meteorological parameters [Johannessen *et al.*, 1997] [Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998].

Figure 28 shows an example of simultaneous SAR and current data collected during the COASTWATCH '95 experiment. The dark wedge-shaped feature at about 57.9° is a cold-water westward-flowing jet associated with upwelling. The research vessel crossed the front at

the south-west side of the jet within a few minutes of the time the SAR image was taken. A peak in the radar backscatter of about 2 dB was observed at the front, and is likely to be due to the enhancement of short surface capillary waves caused by the current shear of about 50 cm/s across the front, as measured by the ship-borne acoustic current profiler.

To investigate this, a number of radar simulation runs were made using the ERIM Ocean Model (EOM), which simulates both the wave-current interaction effects and the electromagnetic wave scattering at the sea surface. The model was also amended to take account of wave breaking processes generating extra centimetre-scale waves. However, the model only predicted a small radar backscatter enhancement (≈ 0.4 dB) when the observed current field was used. If an artificially ‘sharpened’ current field with the same change in current but over a shorter distance was used (50 m, rather than the 1.7 km over which the observed current could be resolved), the backscatter enhancement increased to approximately 1 dB, and this figure could be further increased if a component of convergence at the front was added to the shear.

To make further progress at a fundamental level in improving this radar backscattering modelling product for the SAR expression of current-related features, it may be necessary to use more sophisticated wave generation/evolution, wave-current interaction (including the effect of wave breaking), and radar backscattering models. However, for practical purposes we may still need to trace ‘features’ from image to image in order to estimate currents quantitatively. There is still a requirement for more detailed experimental evaluation of the model simulations. *In situ* measurement of surface currents needs to be performed at small spatial scales (finer than 10 m resolution) to validate these models, and detailed observations of short wind waves and atmospheric boundary layer parameters also need to be made.

Sea surface temperature and ocean frontal features

It has been possible to determine sea surface temperatures from satellites since infrared radiometers became available on satellites in the 1970's. The main limitation is cloudcover, which inhibits observation of the sea surface most of the time in Northern Europe. Currently, sea surface temperatures are operationally available from NOAA AVHRR and ERS-2 ATSR, among others, both with a spatial resolution of about 1 km.

The algorithm currently used to derive sea surface temperature is due to [Lauritson *et al.*, 1979]. The radiance is computed from channels 4 or 5 using the two-point linear radiance calibration available from the on-board blackbody and space-view signals, with a nonlinearity correction. The Planck equation and sensor spectral function are used to convert to temperature. Cloud screening is important [Saunders and Kriebel, 1988]. The algorithm has a sensitivity of 0.1–0.2 K, and has less noise than other multichannel algorithms for SST determination.

Comments by end users at the Norwegian user workshop indicate that it is very important to provide interpretations of images supplied to the users. This is indicated in Figure 29 by the temperature scale, and the annotation, indicating the presence of clouds, the direction of the coastal current, and the position of an eddy at an end of a jet in the current. The precise nature of the annotation obviously depends on the end user's particular requirements.

Figures 29–30 show AVHRR images from respectively December 19 1997 (off the west coast of Norway) and September 25 1997 (off the south-west of Ireland). There are indications of a temperature front in the AVHRR image in Figure 30, which correspond to the location of some frontal features (bright lines) shown in the SAR (Figure 31). The frontal structures and internal waves shown in Figure 31 are near the edge of the continental shelf (shelf break), where the sea bottom topography changes sharply, and causes such dynamic phenomena.

Figure 29: A full-resolution AVHRR image calibrated to give sea-surface temperature values. The position of the Norwegian coastal current is given by its associated cooler water, and a more intense jet with an eddy at its tip is also shown. A quicklook database at Dundee Satellite Receiving Station is useful to search for cloud-free NOAA AVHRR images (URL: <http://www.sat.dundee.ac.uk/auth.html>).

Original AVHRR data © NOAA 1997

Figure 30: NOAA AVHRR quick-look, 1997 September 25, 07:41 UTC, showing sea-surface temperature variations (a brighter feature indicated by the arrow) near the south-west coast of Ireland.

Original SAR data © ESA/UK-PAF 1997

Figure 31: ERS-2 SAR SLCI (Single Look Complex Image), West coast of Ireland, 1997 September 29, 11:40 UTC, Descending orbit. The frontal features observed in the AVHRR image (Figure 30) is located in an area of internal waves observed in the SAR image.

Algal bloom

The application of EO data to Algal Bloom Monitoring, an Irish case study

Since the late 1970s there has been a dramatic increase in finfish and shellfish farming in Ireland. The production of farmed salmon has increased from 21 tonnes in 1980 to 11,600 tonnes in 1994. While over the same time the production of rope cultured mussels, *Mytilus edulis*, has increased from 175 tonnes to 4,700 tonnes while the production of the Pacific oyster *Crassostrea gigas* has increased from 60 tonnes to 2,000 tonnes.

The presence of harmful or toxic algal blooms negatively impacts on the aquaculture industry. The algae affect aquaculture production by causing mass mortalities in fish as a result of gill damage, deoxygenation during bloom decay or toxin production. In contrast to the wild fish, the aquaculture fish has no or limited escape possibilities to avoid the harmful algae blooms. Indirect effects can be due to the accumulation of toxins in shellfish under certain circumstances, rendering them unsafe for human consumption.

Current monitoring in Ireland involves a programme to monitor the presence of natural phytoplankton toxins in Irish shellfish and the analysis of seawater for the presence of toxin producing phytoplankton. The programme is designed to detect toxicity in shellfish growing areas before harvesting, thereby providing information to restrict the placing of toxic shellfish on the market. The current monitoring strategy for bloom events adopted by the Fisheries Research Centre (Marine Institute) is a reactive rather than a proactive one. Earth observational data in the form of MOS², SeaWiFS, AVHRR and SAR data could be integrated to provide an early warning system for bloom monitoring in Ireland.

It is with this primary objective in mind that we have looked at a number of significant algal bloom events that have occurred in the south west of Ireland over the last number of years. We have attempted to utilise AVHRR (movement of water masses, location of fronts), SAR (location of fronts and surface films) and MOS imagery (location of algal blooms and oceanographic fronts). These were utilised independently and/or collectively to learn more about the dynamics of these bloom events and to assess the suitability of EO data in the monitoring of these harmful algal blooms (HABs) in Ireland. The two bloom events that we looked at include:

- *Noctiluca scintillans* bloom event in the Kenmare Bay/Bantry Bay area that was recorded between 23–29 September 1997. This was clearly visible and gave a bright orange/yellow colour to the water. Cell counts of up to 2.4 million cells/litre were recorded.
- *Alexandrium tamarense*, a PSP toxin producer, which occurred in Cork Harbour around 24 June 1996. Cell counts of up to 850,000 cells/litre were recorded. [Personnel Communication Dr. Terry McMahon, Fisheries Research Centre].

²The MOS (Modular Optoelectronic Scanner) sensor is a spaceborne imaging spectrometer for the visible and near infrared part of the spectrum built by DLR Institute for Space Sensor Technology in Germany. The sensor was launched on board the Indian Remote Sensing Satellite IRS-P3 in March 1996. The sensor has 13 channels in the visible and near-infrared (408 - 1010 nm), making the sensor ideal for the remote sensing of coastal zones, where the wide variety of water constituents make analysis of spectral data more complex. The resolution is roughly 1 km, and the swath width is 200 km. In comparison, the American SeaWiFS has only 8 channels (412 - 865 nm), a similar resolution and a swath width of 2000 km.

We would hope that the information gained from such a study could be utilised by the Fisheries Research Centre to assist them in the design of a monitoring system for algal blooms, by allowing them to:

- Act in a proactive rather than reactive manner
- Provide a forecasting service with respect to the movement (advection) of algal bloom events
- Enabling the aquaculture industry to harvest shellfish / finfish before the arrival of harmful algal blooms thus minimising the economic and health impacts of the blooms in the region

The features in the MOS image shown in Figure 32 coincide geographically with the approximate location of the Irish Shelf Front [Huang and Davies, 1991]. The Irish Shelf Front, whose location can be defined by the 35.3 isohaline, separates Irish coastal waters from oceanic waters further offshore. The surface signature of the Irish Shelf Front lies between 20 and 35 km off the coast at about 51°30'N. It is thought that the front is a major influence on the physical and biological processes off south west Ireland. This front again appears to be quite evident in the SAR imagery taken on the 29th of September 1997 (Figure 31).

Figure 32: MOS image obtained on 3rd May 1998 possibly depicting the presence of the Irish Shelf Front (in the lower part of the image), which has a major influence on physical and biological processes in the region.

Figure 33: MOS imagery of Southern Ireland showing a large bloom event on 3rd May 1998 (bright area in the lower, right part of the image). The white areas are clouds.

Table 9: Recent algae blooms in Irish waters causing closures of shellfish growing areas.

Year	Duration of closure
1984	August - October
1985	No closure
1986	No closure
1987	August - December
1988	June - November
1989	June - September
1990	July - October
1991	June - November
1992	June - September
1993	June - September
1994	May - February
1995	June - September
1996	September

A Recent Shellfish Closure

The need for an algal bloom monitoring system is evident by the frequency and duration of closures of shellfish growing areas in Ireland due to the presence of DSP toxins (Table 9).

The recent closure of the mussel production area in Bantry Bay in early May, 1998 was based on a positive bioassay test for the presence of Diarrhetic Shellfish Poison (DSP) toxins in a sample of mussels from the area. Following two further negative weekly test results the area was re-opened. The positive result was not associated with an algal bloom event.

MOS imagery obtained by ARGOSS during the recent period in which the shellfish fishery in Bantry was closed shows features which can be interpreted as large algal events both along the coast and offshore (Figure 33). Communication with the Fisheries Research Centre indicated the following:

*On the 7th May we got a report of discoloured water in the Union Hall/ Glandore area from a local fisherman (Colin Barnes) and on the 8th May we went down and took several samples and photographs. The water was very green and all the samples contained *Phaeocystis* spp. that we have identified as *Phaeocystisglobosa*. It is more than likely therefore that the 'green patch' in the area south of Cork and along the Cork coast shown on the image taken on the 3rd May is showing the extent of this bloom. We were not aware that the bloom was so geographically extensive.*

The availability of images like this really helps in mapping the extent of the bloom, which would be virtually impossible with conventional sampling methods. [Personnel Communication, Dr. Terry McMahon, Fisheries Research Centre].

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1997

Figure 34: Subscene of ERS-2 SAR image from 19 December 1997 covering an area of 30 by 30 km in the North Sea, some 80 km west-southwest of Fedje. Bright spots in the SAR image indicating platforms or supply ships on the Troll platform field are marked in the annotation on the right, as are linear features representing dark backscatter signatures.

Surface slicks and oil spill monitoring

Oil slicks are observable in SAR images as dark signatures. However, several other man-made and natural phenomena give rise to similar signatures making the detection of oil slicks a complicated operation. Nevertheless, a lot of progress has been made in this field and the State Pollution Control Authority (SFT) in Norway routinely uses interpreted SAR images provided by TSS in their oil spill surveillance [Wahl *et al.*, 1994]. Potential oil spill signatures, their location, time, shape and extent, are reported to SFT's operational surveillance aircraft. The aircraft may then perform a dedicated flight to check the potential spill location. This both improves the monitoring capability and increases the efficiency in use of aircraft flight hours.

SAR is able to image ocean surface films caused by the presence of natural surfactant materials. These give rise to areas of reduced backscatter, in the same way as oil spills do, but their intensity and also the shapes of the film areas can usually be distinguished visually from those of oil slicks. The potential importance of SAR observations of natural surface films in monitoring biological activity in coastal waters, for the benefit of fisheries and aquaculture interests is currently investigated. Study of several hundred SAR images shows that natural surface films are generally more common in biologically productive coastal waters than in the open ocean.

Surface slicks observed during the COASTMON project

On 19 December 1997 a full resolution ERS-2 SAR scene was obtained from Tromsø Satellite Station (TSS), and a subscene of this image is shown in Figure 34. The bright spots on the SAR image are from oil platforms and supply or transportation ships in the Troll platform area in the North Sea. The dark signatures connected to some of these spots are believed to be produced water (i.e. water that was pumped up from the reservoir together with the oil during production), as similar signature have been observed in this area before, and it is known that the production platforms release produced water [Espedal, 1998]. In Figure 34, the production platform is located farthest north, while a gas platform is located in the right part of the image.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1996

Figure 35: Subscene of the ERS-2 SAR image from the North Sea on 30 April 1996 (10:47GMT), the necessary wind history, sketches of the slick shape when exposed to low winds causing the slick to diffuse, and the available wind history from a selected point (below). The subscene covers about 10x10km.

Surface slicks in the North Sea

Other studies have shown that knowledge of the wind history is useful when analysing SAR images for potential oil spills [Hamre *et al.*, 1997, Hamre *et al.*, 1995]. A subset of an ERS-2 image from 30 April 1996 centered around 57.7°N, 4.5°E is shown in Figure 35. The angular slick shape is typical for an oil spill which has been exposed to shifting wind directions. Use of the wind history analysis supports this assumption, even if the slick has a slightly different shape as the diffusion of part b (see Figure 35, right) is closest to the source instead or closest to the bend.

Figure 36 shows another ERS-2 SAR image with slicks, and its associated wind history. The SAR image contains a slick which is clearly distinct from its surroundings. This slick is connected to a bright spot which is the Ula platform in the Norwegian sector of the North Sea [Hamre *et al.*, 1995]. The sharp angle of the slick makes it a likely candidate for oil spills.

By looking at the wind history, we find that the wind changed direction (at time T1; in Figure 36, from north-western to western, about 2 hours before the image was taken (at time T2). This change of wind direction corresponds to the sharp bend of the slick, meaning that the part of the slick connected to the platform was generated after the wind turned, while the longest part of the slick is older. Before 06:00GMT on November 25 the slick was exposed to a wind of about 7.5m/s for at least 3 hours, and probably longer since the wind the day before was about 15m/s at noon. If the slick contained natural film, it would have been broken up

Figure 36: Example of angular winding slick in SAR imagery (25.11.94, 10:50GMT) and associated wind history. Image size is 25 km by 25 km.

and dispersed by the strong wind. This slick however, remains connected, and has a sharp gradient to the surrounding area. Thus, the wind history indicates that the slick is man-made and was generated before 09:00GMT (when the wind turned). The shape of the slick shows that much of the material was released before the wind direction changed, as the part of the slick generated before the wind turned is about twice as long as the part generated afterwards. From the wind history, as given in Figure 36, we deduce that the slick may be nearly a day old, since there was another significant change in wind direction at that time but no corresponding bend on the slick.

Based on the analysis presented above, we conclude that the slick is man-made, at least 2 hours old and maximum 23 hours old. With a more detailed wind history, it might be possible to determine the age of the slick more accurately. This particular slick was confirmed to contain oil or oil-based material [Espedal *et al.*, 1995], due to problems with a drilling well on the Ula platform. However, no information was available on how long these problems lasted, or how much oil or oil-based material were released into the ocean.

Synergy of EO techniques

Introduction

In collaboration with the University of Southampton, NERSC performed a study for ESA on The synergetic use of infrared, optical and microwave remote sensing observations, for both open ocean and coastal areas. NERSC is applying to COASTMON the results of this study in the use of combinations of different EO techniques to enhance the value of the data products.

Table 10 shows the types of synergetic remote sensing techniques investigated, and their value.

Product examples

Figure 37 is a NOAA AVHRR thermal infra-red image sequence at 24-hour intervals south of Norway, showing the evolution of the eddies in the Norwegian coastal current (the dark, low sea-surface temperature region, in which the flow is generally toward the west) and the eddies and fronts associated with it. In the Tandem phase of ERS-1 and ERS-2 (May 1995 — May 1996), it was also possible on occasion to obtain SAR images at a 24-hour (or closer) separation. An example of such a sequence is shown in Figure 38, and a number of fronts between different water masses can also be seen as rather bright boundaries around 30–50 km south-west of the Norwegian coast. The combined AVHRR/SAR image (Figure 39) shows how the frontal features are associated with sea-surface temperature changes.

Figure 40 shows a concept of how one may take advantage of remote sensing synergy for pilot monitoring systems.

Table 10: Examples of synergetic remote sensing

Synergy	Phenomena detected/ measured	Result of study
SAR, thermal IR and altimeter (TOPEX/-POSEIDON)	Sea-surface height, meso-scale circulation features	The potential advantages of synergy remain speculative
SAR and thermal IR	large & meso-scale circulation features,	Useful complementary information, can be associated with bathymetry
ERS-1,2 SAR tandem	Highly dynamic features such as current fronts	Synergy advantageous, though interpretation remains speculative

Original AVHRR data © NOAA 1995

Figure 37: NOAA AVHRR thermal infra-red image sequence south of Norway, 1995 September 19–21.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1995

Figure 38: ERS-1/2 SAR tandem pair from south-southwest of Norway, 1995 September 30.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1995 Original AVHRR data © NOAA 1995

Figure 39: Synergetic use of AVHRR thermal infra-red and ERS-1 SAR data south of Norway, 1995 September 30.

Figure 40: Concept of a pilot monitoring system in a synergetic remote sensing perspective.

WP3: User demonstrations

The purpose of the user demonstration activities were to show results of the product development work in WP3 to a wider community including end users who are expected to apply new satellite data in the future. Demonstrations have been carried out for Norwegian, Irish and Dutch users in form of direct demonstration at end users location and during specific events such as oil spill accidents and algal blooms. Results have also been shown at the specific user workshops and at conferences where a wider user community has been approached.

Norwegian demonstrations

The demonstration in Norway were based on a 2.5-month study from November 1997 to February 1998 integrating meteorological observations, numerical atmospheric, wave, and current models, remote sensing observations, and a wave radar located at the Fedje VTS station. This station is selected as the key end user for metocean data because it controls marine traffic to and from the oil refinery at Mongstad and the nearby oil and gas terminals. Contact with the VTS station was made on a routine basis by DNMI, which provides operational forecasts of meteorological, wave, and current conditions. The VTS terminal may be occasionally closed for traffic as a result of adverse weather and wave conditions. Improved knowledge of local topographically-induced wind, wave, and current conditions can aid the navigation of VLCCs and other large vessels and structures through this area.

The demonstrated products included:

- Wave observations from ground-based radar ($2\frac{1}{2}$ months starting on 1997 November 25)
- Directional wave analysis from SAR, including evolution/propagation
- Wind analysis from SAR, including local variability
- Sea temperature patterns from NOAA-AVHRR
- Waves and currents from DNMI's numerical models
- An indication of the current patterns from the SAR images

Three ERS-2 images and two Radarsat images were obtained for the demonstration period.

Land-based wave radar

The wave radar at Fedje is an ordinary ship radar. The information on the sea clutter is used to calculate a 3-dimensional wave spectrum in the following way: A 2-dimensional spatial Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is executed on each of 32 radar scans, and then a temporal FFT is executed on the the time series of FFT'ed images. In this way a spectrum without directional ambiguity is obtained. The 3-dimensional wavenumber-frequency spectrum is integrated along the frequency axis to obtain a two dimensional wavenumber spectrum. This 2-dimensional spectrum can be converted from wavenumber representation to frequency-direction representation i.e. a spectrum telling how much energy there is at each frequency and direction band. This spectrum can be compared to spectra from numerical wave forecast models.

The software to obtain wave spectra from radar raw data is developed by GKSS-Forschungszentrum, Germany, and the system is called WaMoS (Wave Monitoring System).

Case studies

The first case of synergetic study of satellite SAR and meteorological forecastings was from December 19, 1997, when SAR, AVHRR, wind forecast, and wave forecast were obtained on the west coast of Norway (Figure 41).

The meteorological forecast (Figure 41(a)) indicated south-easterly winds 5 m/s at Fedje, with 1.2 m swell from south. The wave forecast (Figure 41(b)) indicate less than 1.5 m significant wave height in the area. The direct wind observations at Fedje showed more easterly winds, which agrees with the observations in the SAR image, showing an easterly wind plume coming out of Sognefjorden. The wave spectra from the SAR image also showed northerly propagating waves with wavelengths up to 200 m and significant wave height around 1.0 m. The AVHRR image showed sea surface temperature under cloudfree conditions on the west coast indicating the northward propagating coastal current as a plume of colder water, with eddied and meanders, compared to the warmer Atlantic water located further east. No current features could be observed in the SAR image which resembled the temperature structure seen in the AVHRR image. The most important result from this case study was the wind direction observed in from SAR which was more accurate near the coast than what the meteorological forecast indicated. The wind speed analysis from SAR was in good agreement with the meteorological prediction as well as with the in situ observations.

Another case study was performed on 15 January 1998, when the winds were southerly, parallel to the coast. The SAR image show pronounced wind shadows (dark patches in the coastal and fjord regions) which indicated that wind direction was southerly (Figure 42(c)). At Fedje, the wind speed prediction as well as in situ observation was 3 m/s which agreed well with the SAR wind speed analysis (Figure 42(d)).

The SAR image also showed clear ocean frontal features oriented nearly perpendicular to the coast (Figure 42(c)). Such features are most likely associated with eddies which tend to create temperature fronts visible in IR-images (such as Figure 41(d)). Mapping of fronts by SAR imagery is important because these fronts and associated eddies can represent the highest current speeds in the area, which have significant impact in the navigation of larger tankers to and from Mongstad oil refinery.

On February 6, 1998, wave spectra could also be obtained from the coastal radar at Fedje, as a supplement to the meteorological forecasts (Figure 43(a)). The wind and wave conditions were more severe than in the two other cases, with 14-15 m/s southerly winds and significant wave height of 3.7 m at Fedje. The wave directional spectrum from the coastal radar (Figure 43(a)) showed southerly to westerly waves with peak energy at a period of 11 seconds. A Radarsat SAR image with fine resolution (about 10 m pixel size) was on this day for a 40x40 km area around Fedje island (Figure 43(c)). This image showed the swell propagation from west towards the coast very clearly, including refraction and decay of the waves as they went through straits into the fjords. The high resolution Radarsat images have better capability to map waves with wavelengths from 20 m to 100 m compared to the ERS images. Radarsat has also capability to obtain SAR images over a specific region more frequently than ERS.

Other demonstrations towards users in Norway was carried out during the FARGIS/POSEIDON meeting in Oslo, 19 January 1999. These demonstrations are further described below.

Figure 41: Norwegian location, 1997 December 19

(a) 12-hour forecast for wind from HIRLAM atmospheric model with 10 km resolution

(b) Significant wave height forecast from WAM wave model

(c) ERS SAR image taken at 11h UTC.

(d) Sea-surface temperature from NOAA AVHRR channel 4, 12:34 UTC; location of ERS SAR marked with a rectangle.

Forecast for Fedje location, Meteorological analysis, HIRLAM/WINCH: Wind: SE 5m/s, Hs: 1.4m, Tz: 7s, Swell: 1.2m, 9s from South

Observations: Troll NE 3m/s, 2.5m, 7s. Hellisøy (the island just south of Fedje): E 3 m/s

ERS SAR data © ESA/TSS 1998

Figure 42: Norwegian location, 1998 January 15.

(a) 3-hour forecast for wind from HIRLAM atmospheric model with 50 km resolution, January 15, 21h UTC.

(b) 6-hour forecast of significant wave height from WAM model, for 18h UTC.

(c) 100×100 km ERS SAR image with the Fedje–Mongstad area at the bottom of the image, 21h UTC. Note that the image is oriented with north-north-west at the top, and the satellite look direction is from the left, as we are in the ascending orbit (satellite moving from SSE to NNW).

(d) Wind speed, using the CMOD-4 algorithm from ERS SAR data.

Meteorological analysis, HIRLAM/WINCH: Wind: S 3m/s, Hs: 1.9m, Tz: 6.6s, Swell: 1.9m 11s from SSW

Observations—Troll: SSE 8m/s, 2.5m, 6s. Helleøy: E 3m/s

RADARSAT SAR data © Radarsat International 1998

Figure 43: Norwegian location, 1998 February 6

(a) Wave directional spectrum from the microwave radar at Fedje, 15h UTC.

(b) 6-hour wind forecast, 18h UTC

(c) Part of RADARSAT image with the island of Fedje at the centre, and swell waves visible.

Analysis, HIRLAM/WINCH: Wind: S 14m/s, Hs: 3.7m, Tz: 7.0s Swell 1.6m, 10s from SW

No obs from Troll. Hellisøy: S 15m/s. Gullfaks: S 13m/s, 4m, 7s

COASTMON user demonstration, Norway, Høvik, 1999 January 19

1. Introduction

In addition to the COASTMON Norwegian demonstration of EO data products and model results, a presentation was made in poster form at a one-day meeting held near Oslo: the FARGIS/POSEIDON user seminar. The meeting was held on 1999 January 19, hosted by Det norske Veritas at their headquarters in Høvik, near Oslo, and organized by the SINTEF Department of Civil Engineering.

FARGIS (Farledgeografisk informasjonssystem) is a co-operative programme between state institutions, industry, and research institutes, which aims to co-ordinate and encourage the use of information technology (IT) to ensure safer and more effective marine transport.

The meeting included a presentation of the results of the POSEIDON project, which is an EU-funded maritime and intermodal project, aiming to establish tools, principles, standards and architecture for interoperability of VTS at local, regional and European levels.

The meeting was attended by 130 participants from Norway and 8 other countries. All the participants were associated in some way with the shipping industry. The following organizations were represented:

- The Department of Fisheries in Norway
- The Norwegian State Pollution Control Authority
- The Norwegian and Swedish Directorates for Maritime Affairs
- The Norwegian Coast Directorate
- The Norwegian naval authorities
- The Research Council of Norway
- The Harbour Boards of Oslo, Grenland, Borg, and Brønnøy
- The Electronic Chart Centre
- The Norwegian Mapping Authority
- The Norwegian Meteorological Institute
- Horten VTS
- Havarikommisjonen for fiskeflåten (responsible for investigating shipwrecks in the fishing fleet)
- Shipping companies, including Color Line and Fred Olsen
- Oil companies, including Statoil and Esso
- The fisheries press
- Research institutes and consultancies, including SINTEF, NERSC, DERA (UK), ABP Research & Consultancy (UK), Inst. of Ship Operation Sea Transport & Simulation (Germany), TRUTh SA (Greece)

- Classification societies (DnV)
- Industrial companies, including manufacturers of navigation equipment (NAVTEK A/S, C-map NOR, Kongsberg Norcontrol, Vetis AS, Vector AS, Scanteam International AS, VTT Manufacturing Technology (Finland), Enyca Engineering & Communications SA (Spain), STN Atlas Elektronikk (Denmark))
- Survey companies (Fugro Geoteam AS)
- Telecommunication companies (Telenor AS (Norway), INMARSAT, Community Network Services (UK))
- Norwegian pilots' association
- Transport companies (Helikopter Service AS, KP-distribusjon AS)
- Institutes of higher education (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece))
- International organizations, including the CEC DG XIII, and IALA (International Association of Lighthouse Authorities)

2. FARGIS seminar

The following topics were presented and discussed:

- Ship reporting / HAZMAT
- Weather information via WWW
- Traffic centres as information centres
- Risk analysis
- Quality and standardization
- Global development of ECDIS (electronic charts)
- Ship tracking by transponder and by INMARSAT

3. Poseidon presentation

The POSEIDON project is funded by the Telematics Application Programme of the European Commission, under the Transport Sector (project number TR1041). Its objectives are to establish the principles, standards and architecture for the interoperability of maritime Vessel traffic Systems (VTS) at local, regional and European level by the integration of VTS with advanced vessel communications, information and tracking technologies in order to improve the safety and efficiency of maritime transport. The co-ordinating institution is the Transeuropean Consulting Unit of Thessaloniki S.A. (TRUTh).

The project consortium consists of 12 organizations from Greece, Germany, the UK, Spain, Finland, Sweden, and Norway, and sponsoring partners include port authorities, shipping companies and agencies, and local and national authorities, from six countries. The project web page is on <http://hermes.civil.auth.gr/poseidon/poseidon.html> .

The following topics were presented and discussed:

- The POSEIDON project and scope
- The POSEIDON compendium
- Poseidon demonstration evaluation framework and results
- The Norwegian POSEIDON site demonstrator. This is at the Horten VTS station on Oslofjord.

There were also presentations on European and Norwegian perspectives on maritime IT, by the CEC and the Norwegian Research Council.

4. COASTMON presentation

Figures 44-45 show the poster presentation of COASTMON made at the seminar. These were displayed prominently, next to a poster stand produced by DNMI, and were thus viewed by the 130 participants associated with the Norwegian and international shipping industry.

Points raised by the participants, relating to COASTMON, were as follows:

- There was interest in the capability of SAR and other EO techniques to chart sea ice in waters such as those around Spitzbergen, for the benefit of the fishing fleet
- There was interest in the use of such techniques as numerical modelling and EO, to monitor the behaviour of ocean currents near the coast for the benefit of ship navigation, oil spill prediction, etc.
- There were a number of specific questions about the availability of SAR and other EO data from the various satellite ground stations including Tromsø Satellite station, including the price and whether they could be obtained in near-real time.

COASTMON

METOCEAN AND COASTAL ZONE MONITORING USING SATELLITE RADAR

Co-ordinator: Alastair Jenkins, NERSC
 WWW page: <http://www.nrsc.no/COASTMON>

Overall objective:

To explore and test methods for use of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and other new satellite data, and their integration with geographical information systems (GIS), in monitoring environmental/metocean conditions in regions close to harbours trafficked by very large vessels, to improve navigational safety, to aid coastal zone management (CZM), and to improve utilization of satellite observations in the user community.

Specific objectives are:

- To identify gaps between current environmental monitoring products and user requirements, in port and harbour areas
- To evaluate the user of satellite data to improve MetOcean monitoring around ports and harbours, with emphasis on satellite radars and their synergetic use with other data and numerical models, and their integration with GIS for coastal zone management (CZM)
- To demonstrate new satellite data products, their integration with GIS and CEO's enabling services, to involve a wider user group for the products
- To assess and recommend new satellite products for use in MetOcean monitoring and CZM for harbour regions

Partners:

- Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), NORWAY
- Advisory and Research Group on Geo Observation Systems and Services (ARGOSS), THE NETHERLANDS
- The Norwegian Meteorological Institute (DNMI), NORWAY
- Coastal Resources Centre, University College, Cork (CRC-UCC), IRELAND

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 www: <http://www.ucc.ie/research/crc>

This is a shared-cost project which is part-funded under Area 3 (CEO programme) of the Environment and Climate programme of the European Commission. The project runs from February 1997 to March 1999.

EC contact points:

- P. Churchill (CEO programme), Peter.Churchill@jrc.it
- G. Sawyer (Area 3.3), Geoff.Sawyer@dg12.cec.be

If you would like further information about the CEO programme or other shared cost action projects, please go to the CEO Home Page (<http://www.ceo.org/>) or the EWSE (<http://ewse.ceo.org/>).

Figure 44: First page of COASTMON poster presented at FARGIS/POSEIDON seminar.

Figure 45: Second page of COASTMON poster presented at FARGIS/POSEIDON seminar.

Irish demonstrations

CEO funded training course

At the initial COASTMON project user-requirements workshops a lack of awareness of the potential uses of EO data amongst the Irish coastal management community was identified. The Coastal Resources Centre, in conjunction with the Centre for Earth Observation, ran a five day training course from the 18th - 22nd of January 1999 on the use of earth observational data. The course entitled "Earth-Observation Information and its application to Coastal Management in Ireland 'A Training Course for Irish end-users'" was attended by a variety of end users who had been identified within the COASTMON project as potential users of EO data. The course was given by a selection of international speakers with experience in the use and application of earth observation data. Datasets derived from the COASTMON project were discussed during the course. Course speakers came from a variety of organisations and included individuals from the Nansen Centre, our partners in the COASTMON project and individuals representing the Irish Marine Data Centre and Earth Observation Systems (EOS) partners in the ICAMS project also funded by the Centre for Earth Observation.

Course participants

Course participants came from a variety of organisations and had a variety of experience in the use of earth observation information. Many of the organisations who sent staff on the course were identified in the original COASTMON proposal as being potential users of EO data. These organisations included, the Irish Naval Service, The Marine Institute, The Marine Data Centre, the Fisheries Research Centre, the state fisheries board (BIM), the Coastal Local Authorities, Harbour Masters and the Environmental Protection Agency. In addition a number of academic groups sent participant and these included researchers in the fields of biology, engineering, geography, geology and hydrology. A list of course attendees is given in Table 11.

Aspects of the training course involved discussions between end-users, the course organisers (the CRC) and the course lecturers on the possibilities which existed in terms of the use of EO data and potential applications. The following is a summary of one of the discussions held as part of the course:

- **Navy Ship Movement Monitoring**

Brian Fitzgerald (Naval Service) The timing of the images and the image quality are perceived as the restrictions of the use of EO data for Navy purposes. The Naval Service (NS) is reluctant to be seen to be monitoring ship movement, in this respect satellite data has an advantage over the more visible airborne methods.

Stein Sandven (NERSC) The Tromsø receiving station in Norway is now working on fast delivery of data (1 hour).

Brian Fitzgerald (NS) The timing of the imagery is vital. Satellite orbits aren't flexible enough. The NS is setting up a transponder system so imagery is available every two hours. However, satellite data may be useful to give an overall picture of the situation and to highlight discrepancies with the transponder information. The navy currently has two dedicated maritime aircraft using optical and radar sensors. These can transmit to ground stations and information can be received by relevant people in very short time

Table 11: CRC training course participants.

Name	Affiliation
Dr. Bret Danilowicz	Department of Zoology, University College Dublin
Ms. Anne Marie Hayes	The Irish Marine Data Centre
Mr. Cormac Parle	The Irish Marine Data Centre
Mr. Ronan Cosgrove	Fisheries Development Division, Bord Iascaigh Mhara
Ms. Yvonne Shields	Programme Manager, Water-Based Tourism & Leisure, Marine Institute
Lt. Brian Fitzgerald	Fisheries Legislation Mngr, National Supervisory Cntr, The Naval Service
Ms. Niamh Farrell	Bord Iascaigh Mhara
Mr. Joe Silke	Fisheries Research Centre, Marine Institute
Capt. Jerry Desmond	Bantry Harbour Master
Mr. Paul Colman	Senior Scientific Officer, Environmental Protection Agency
Mr. Noel O Murachu	Dept. of the Marine & Natural Resources
Mr. John O Keeffe	Dept. of the Marine & Natural Resources
Mr. Damian Brosnan	Environment Section, Cork County Council
Mr. Mick Mackey	Aquaculture Development Centre, UCC
Mr. Jerry Sutton	Coastal Resources Centre, UCC
Mr. David Joyce	Dept. of Geography, UCC
Capt. Pat Farnan	Harbour Master, Port of Cork
Capt. Micheal McCarthy	Chief Engineer, Port of Cork
Mr. Paul Stampf	
Mr. John Martin	Dept. of Civil & Env. Engineering, UCC
Mr. Brian Holmes	Hydraulics & Maritime Research Centre, UCC

via email. There is no use for EO data in its current form - need high resolution and real time access.

Des Murphy (GKSS) A nested solution might be a possibility - where EO data was part of a range of monitoring capabilities including satellite data and air data.

Brian Fitzgerald (NS) In terms of drug traffic monitoring there might be a use for once-off reference to satellite imagery. They do not have the budget to invest in a system for such an irregular requirement so the information would have to be easily accessible in a pre-processed form.

Stein Sandven (NERSC) The Norwegian navy use SAR to supplement air monitoring. They use this to receive images roughly once a day in more remote areas.

Brian Fitzgerald (NS) Due to cloud and the infrequency of the orbits, satellite coverage is not reliable enough in Ireland.

Des Murphy (GKSS) Air borne sensors are more appropriate for Irish requirements.

Stein Sandven (NERSC) The reservations of Irish potential users should be expressed to the satellite agencies so that they can consider them in future planning.

- **Oil Spill Monitoring**

Des Murphy (GKSS) For monitoring oil spills particularly air borne sensors are ideal.

Jerry Desmond (Bantry Harbour Master) Dropping transponders into the middle of an oil spill is the best way to monitor it. Or as the Germans do make regular flights with fleets of aircraft with multi-spectral scanners.

Paul Colman (EPA) The most important factor in monitoring an oil spill is the tide tables. Reference to a LANDSAT scene might give general information but tide is the most important factor.

Eddie O'Leary (CRC) Satellite data is most useful for monitoring offshore incidents. Information may not be available frequently enough at the moment, but it will be in the

near future.

- **Ballast Discharge & Water Plume Monitoring** *Jerry Desmond (Bantry Harbour Master)* Janet Nichol's approach to monitoring the discharge of yellow substance might be applicable to monitoring ballast discharge, as there is probably a temperature difference involved.

Stein Sandven (NERSC) We must be realistic about the capabilities of EO data. When it is used to supplement other monitoring techniques it can result in better management of monitoring resources.

Jerry Desmond (Bantry Harbour Master) Could the pattern of coastal plumes be established from SAR to help establish the extent of pollutants and find where clear water exists?

Janet Nichol (UCC) Some plumes don't necessarily have a temperature difference, or they may be seasonal. In Macau the plumes were used to establish the extent of the freshwater in the sea.

Martin Critchley (ERA Maptec) The discharge of water into Dublin bay is visible on M.S.S. data.

Jerry Desmond (Bantry Harbour Master) Even if these images are infrequent, over time a picture can be built up.

- **Algal Bloom Monitoring** *Cormac Pearle (MDC)* Interested in fact that Norway uses ships to monitor algal bloom rather than satellites

Des Murphy (GKSS) Multi-spectral sensors are most suited to monitoring algal bloom - are used in the BIOPTIS project. Satellite data offers a valuable contribution at a small.

Anne-Marie Hayes (MDC) In the COLOURS project they are trying to develop a database of in situ data to develop algorithms for ocean colour. When COLOURS is over they will work on other algorithms.

Joe Silke (FRC) DSP species, in which he is interested most problematic - not a good candidate for EO, but might see associated features.

Des Murphy (GKSS) In tidal flat monitoring generally look for proxy parameters

Joe Silke (FRC) He would like to see satellite images of the annual occurrence of contamination in Cork Harbour.

Martin Critchley (ERA Maptec) Is the requirement for continuous monitoring or for detailed coverage during an event?

Joe Silke (FRC) Both

- **Coastal Zone Monitoring**

Des Murphy (GKSS) In Germany, Holland and Denmark the TMAC is a monitoring agreement about issues of concern. From this they prioritise monitoring parameters. A consensus is needed in Ireland between interested parties involved in coastal issues about priority issues.

Niamh Connolly (CRC) and Yvonne Shields(MI) The 1997 Bradey, Shipman & Martin report and the recent Marine Institute Policy document contain a commitment to integrated coastal zone management. However, as yet these commitments have not been implemented.

John O'Keefe (DoMNR) Although he will be directly involved in the implementation of any Government commitment to integrated coastal zone management he was not consulted in the BSM report. There is in general too much emphasis on terrestrial planning in any coastal zone management issues.

- **Fisheries**

Niamh Farrell (BIM) BIM would not currently have a use of EO data; they would require real time info.

Ronan Cosgrove (BIM) Temperature front information would be of interest. These would probably be obtained by getting EO consultants to provide the information.

- **Water Quality Monitoring**

Paul Colman (EPA) The EPA is responsible for water quality monitoring. At the moment they monitor most estuaries. Satellite data would be useful as they could miss an algal bloom event. If algal blooms occur they would like to be informed so they could go out and do ship based monitoring.

- **Oceanography**

Bret Danilowicz (UCD) Satellite data can be useful for oceanography. However, the initial work on establishing model must be done before the satellite data can be used.

Des Murphy (GKSS) The COLOURS project will establish some of these models.

Jerry Sutton (CRC) Some of these physical models already exist: the WAM model at a national scale and various local hydrographic models.

Des Murphy (GKSS) It is algorithm rather than models that are required.

Niamh Connolly (CRC) The CEO is currently compiling information about existing algorithms and their application.

Martin Critchley (ERA Maptec) The restrictions on optical data in Ireland are clouds and poor winter visibility. The problem with radar data is the low number of repeats. The only frequent systems are AVHRR and SeaWifs. SAR availability won't increase in the immediate future, as SAR is very expensive to launch. The next stage of development will be polar platforms.

Brian Fitzgerald (NS) The best system that he has seen so far this week has been the Enterprise Ireland air photos. How can this be bettered by satellite images?

Martin Critchley (ERA Maptec) Resolution of satellites will improve dramatically this year with ICONIS giving real time delivery at 1m black and white and 3m colour in the optical sensors. SAR will be available at 10m resolution.

Des Murphy (GKSS) The cost of these satellites may restrict their use.

Table 12 shows which material was presented to the participants which was related to this project.

In addition practical elements of the course focused on areas which had been identified in our initial meetings with end users as being of particular interest to them. These areas included SST, oil spill monitoring and algal bloom monitoring.

Collaborations

Ongoing development of links between the COASTMON and ICAMS project. In 1998, the Coastal Resources Centre, facilitated the ICAMS project by organising an ICAMS end user workshop for them in Cork. Following from that initial meeting, an invitation was extended to Graham Bland of the ICAMS project to speak about the results from the ICAMS project to date at the training course. In addition Bronwyn Cahill, the Manager of the Marine Data Centre who is also involved in the ICAMS project was invited to give a presentation.

Development of links between the COASTMON and LIFE project. The algal bloom monitoring data from the COASTMON project will be integrated into the LIFE funded Bantry Bay Charter

Table 12: CRC training course material related to COASTMON.

Subject	Presented by
Data acquisition and availability in an Irish context	Martin Critchley
A review of EO applications in Ireland to-date	Martin Critchley
LACoast - using EO data to monitor coastal change.	Martin Critchley
The Norwegian experience of using microwave data for oil spill and algal bloom monitoring	Stein Sandven
The use of EO data for water quality analysis in Singapore	Janet Nichol
The Norwegian experience of using optical data for deriving sea-state information	Stein Sandven
Irish user-requirements and brain storming on the potential uses of EO data within the organisations of the attendees	Niamh Connolly
EO data for ecological monitoring	Des Murphy
The management of an EO project: the ICAMS ocean colour project in Bantry Bay.	Graham Bland
The use of Earth Observation data in the Irish Marine Data Centre	Bronwyn Cahill

project, which aims to facilitate community involvement in the development of an integrated coastal zone management strategy. Aquaculture is an important local industry that is badly effected by algal bloom events. Although this information will not be available in real-time, the facility to examine previous occurrences may help the local community to better understand the events.

Development of links between the COASTMON and RACER project. The RACER project is examining emergency response procedures in the Irish Sea. The wave climate data produced by the COASTMON project are being assessed for suitability for use in the production of sea state scenarios. These sea state scenarios will be integrated into a vessel traffic management system/GIS for use by the emergency services and small vessel users.

Development of links between the COASTMON and STORMINESS project. The STORMINESS project is identifying sensitive coastal areas in the Atlantic Fringe of the European Union and studying the effect of storms on the coastline for the last 2000 years. There may be potential for collaboration in integrating climatological data and in the numerical modelling of storminess.

End-user workshops

The original results of the BAS processing for Rosslare were disappointing. In view of the high level of interest from Irish end-users in this product, ARGOS have re-processed the data and the new results will be presented to end-users in a series of meetings on the 4th and 5th of March. As part of the ongoing personnel exchanges and project work visits it was arranged for Kees Mastenbrok to attend these meetings. The results of these workshops are presented in WP4.

Results of COASTMON in Ireland

COASTMON - Coastal Resources Centre, University College Cork

The COASTMON project explores methods for the use of synthetic aperture radar and other new satellite data and their integration with GIS to aid CZM and to improve use of satellite observations in the user community. ERS SAR, with a resolution of 25 m has a large potential for observation of many of the important processes; wave spectra, oil spill detection, shallow water bathymetry and ship detection, currents, eddies fronts, flooding, erosion, estuarine tides. The project uses SAR data, which will give qualitative information about the presence and lo-

cation of eddies, fronts, internal waves, ships, oil and natural slicks. SAR data can provide quantitative wind and wave field parameters, but unable to provide current or temperature parameters. The incorporation of satellite as well as in situ observations into coastal zone management plans will be greatly aided by an integration of these data with GIS, to assist the safe development of harbour industrial activities. Work at the CRC has shown that there is a need for quantitative data about ocean current, wind wave and temperature fields. Our user requirements study showed that weather forecasting services, local coastal and harbour authorities with responsibilities for ship traffic, pollution control, fisheries and aquaculture would benefit from acquisition of satellite data. It would be necessary to provide the interpretation of the satellite images for the users, rather than provide the raw images.

Earlier projects at the CRC (such as EPOC) have had greater or lesser elements of CZM decision support built in, with specific reference to coastal dynamics. Other research is on risk analysis, vulnerability assessment, and possible responses to hazards of near future sea level rise in the Cork area, with implications for decision support. In addition, the Bantry Bay Charter Project is a pilot study to develop a community based ICZM strategy for Bantry Bay, compiling existing in situ and RS data within a user friendly GIS, which will ultimately to aid in decision support. The project entitled Storminess, which is about to start, will involve modelling of storm patterns from RS data, with particular reference to Atlantic coast areas of Europe at risk from coastal erosion and flooding.

Use of EO data in coastal zone management

Currently there is limited operational use of satellite data in the Irish coastal zone. It is important for coastal zone decision makers to be aware of the differences between open ocean and coastal zone requirements; the coastal zone scale is from 10m to 100km, a factor of 10 below open ocean. We need to:

1. identify the potential users of a coastal monitoring system, who would use this as a planning and management tool; identify user requirements and user willingness to participate in demonstration products based on RS and other data; assess how RS data can improve coastal monitoring;
2. develop a plan for coastal monitoring service; this would facilitate full use of RS data in an integrated coastal monitoring, forecasting and management service; possible support operations include:
 - providing high resolution maps of surface winds, wind fronts and wind patterns in open ocean and coasts;
 - improved surface wave measurements, especially on propagation and refraction of long waves near coasts and interaction with strong surface current features such as eddies;
 - mapping of current fronts, eddies and other mesoscale circulation patterns; monitoring oil spills;
 - mapping internal waves;
 - contributing to mapping shallow bottom topography;
 - mapping atmospheric boundary layer processes: fronts, waves, wind rolls, rain cells;
 - monitoring ship traffic.

3. integrate products into the monitoring system; importance of GIS for data integration.

Existing RS data sources perceived as of particular relevance to Irish CZM

Currently in the Irish context, SAR, AVHRR, scatterometer and SeaWiFS are useful. However, cloud cover, which can prevail over Ireland for weeks, makes data such as AVHRR, SeaWiFS, SPOT and Landsat practically useless for studies of processes which change within a few days such as ocean currents structures, flooding and algal blooms. METEOSAT is too coarse for coastal zone monitoring; with regard to altimeter and scatterometer data - their resolution is also too coarse for the coastal zone.

ERS-1 and ERS-2 use a variety of sensors - radars and radiometers which aid in monitoring the ocean surface. It may be possible to synergise sea surface temperatures from AVHRR and surface backscatter from ERS SAR. NOAA also provides AVHRR images.

Dutch demonstrations

The Dutch end user workshop was held in October 1998. At this workshop Dutch companies and institutes involved in management and exploration of offshore regions was invited (Table 13). The following products was demonstrated at this workshop:

- the bathymetry assessment system: several examples along the Dutch and Belgian coast.
- the retrieval of high resolution wind fields from SAR imagery: Dutch coastal waters and IJsselmeer.
- an on-line system to assess the wind and wave climate in offshore regions, including spectral wave data from SAR wave mode observations
- demonstration of the capability of the SAR to image waves propagating into harbour areas.

Table 13: ARGOSS evaluation workshop participants.

Name	Affiliation
Ms. E. Bosma	Boskalis/Hydronomic
Mr. C. van Cauwenberghe	Ministry of the Flemish Community, Belgium
Ms. M. van Endt	Svasek
Mr. D.P. Hurdle	Alkyon Hydraulic Consultancy and Research BV
Mr. R. van de Ketterij	HMC, Hydrographic and Marine Consultants BV
Mr. G.H. van der Kolff	BCRS, Netherlands Remote Sensing Board
Ms. C. Koppen	ARGOSS
Mr. C. Mastenbroek	ARGOSS
Mr. C. Vernemmen	University of Gent, Belgium
Mr. A.C. Voorrips	KNMI, Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
Mr. G.J. Wensink	ARGOSS

Part I: Wind and wave data from satellites

The accuracy of swell climates derived from both ships' records and numerical model output is limited. Knowledge about the swell is important for the planning and execution of offshore operations. A limited amount of swell of a particular frequency may cause a platform to resonate, which may disrupt operations.

In numerical models the swell is often poorly represented. In ships' observations swell is often neglected, and only wind sea is reported. A disadvantage of buoys is that many do not report directional information. The propagation direction of in particular the swell is important.

The swell climate is also important input in morphological studies. When climatic values are known at open sea, they are translated to the near shore situation. For this translation the directional information is crucial. At this moment the wave propagation direction reported by the CLAMS system suffers from a 180 degree ambiguity. Near the shore this ambiguity can be resolved by assuming that the swell originates from the open sea. If possible, users would like to see that this is done by CLAMS rather than leave it to the users.

The evaluation of the on-line wave climate system by HMC showed that it is unclear which data are present in the system, and how the user can gain access to these data. The medium Internet is still unfamiliar to many potential users, in particular for serious applications. This

frightens many conservative users because they have no idea what to do. Therefore the most important recommendation is to make not only an on-line help, but also a paper version. In this documentation a comprehensive overview should be given of the quality of the presented data, and of the corrections and manipulations that these data have undergone.

The present structure of the site puts users off initially. It requires some energy to find ones way in the jungle of screens to find the required data. Therefore the on-line help/documentation should be improved. There were also some comments on the contents of the site. Users want percentages rather than actual occurrences in the tables. This make the data more suitable for further processing. Many users also want a measure of the quality and reliability of the data.

The extreme value statistics should be better explained.

There was also some discussion as to what would be the best price policy.

Part II: Bathymetric mapping using remote sensing techniques

The present Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) was presented. Presently the method has some limitations: when there is a lot of detail in the bottom topography the satellite radar images do not always resolve this. In those cases airborne radar images are required. The BAS system is particularly useful to lower the costs of traditional depth measuring campaigns, it can not completely replace them. Independently from BAS radar images can also be used to determine the location of the coastline.

Presently the effort of ARGOSS is focused on the development of an on-line system to assess the applicability of BAS to arbitrary regions around the globe. Obviously BAS can be used to monitor the evolution of the bathymetry in a certain regions over time. This trend can be compared with optical images of the sediment load. By combining these two remote sensing data sets, a comprehensive overview of the present and future situation can be given.

Demonstration of wind and wave climatology product

Users from different companies were enable to assess the wind and wave climate in regions of their interest. The main distribution channel for this service was the Internet. As a part of the COASTMON project an interactive website was set up that allows users to select an arbitrary region. All wind and wave observations acquired in this region by several satellite missions (ERS-1/2, GEOSAT, Topex/Poseidon) and by several sensors (altimeter, scatterometer and SAR) are read from a database. The user has then a wide range of options how climate data should be derived from these data. All computations are performed real time, and the results are presented graphically within a few seconds. The service, named CLAMS, is accessible with standard, Jave-enabled browsers on <http://www.argoss.nl/clams/>.

The CLAMS service was made available to different companies in the Netherlands. These companies covered all important industries that will be targeted with the new on-line service: dredging (Boskalis), heavy lifting (Heerema), off-shore (Shell) and specialised consultancies (HMC, Alkyon). An overview of the companies that participated in the evaluation can be found in Annex ???.

The opinion of the users on the usefulness of the new service was evaluated at a workshop in Zwolle (NL) on October 29, 1998. At this workshop four users of CLAMS were represented (Svasek, Boskalis, Alkyon and HMC). The general opinion was that the accuracy of swell climates derived from both ships' records and numerical model output is too limited. Knowledge about the swell is important for the planning and execution of offshore operations. A limited amount of swell of a particular frequency may cause a platform to resonate, which may disrupt

operations. In numerical models the swell is often poorly represented. In ships' observations swell is often neglected, and only wind sea is reported. A disadvantage of buoys is that many do not report directional information. The propagation direction of in particular the swell is important. The swell climate is also important input in morphological studies. When climatic values are known at open sea, they are translated to the near shore situation. For this translation the directional information is crucial. At this moment the wave propagation direction reported by the CLAMS system suffers from a 180 degree ambiguity. Near the shore this ambiguity can be resolved by assuming that the swell originates from the open sea. If possible, users would like to see that this is done by CLAMS rather than leave it to the users. The evaluation of the on-line wave climate system by HMC showed that it is unclear which data are present in the system, and how the user can gain access to these data. The medium Internet is still unfamiliar to many potential users, in particular for serious applications. This frightens many conservative users because they have no idea what to do. Therefore the most important recommendation is to make not only an on-line help, but also a paper version. In this documentation a comprehensive overview should be given of the quality of the presented data, and of the corrections and manipulations that these data have undergone.

Products demonstrated during WP3

Some of the products ARGOS demonstrated to users during WP3 are shown in the description of the product development workpackage (WP2). For instance, the BAS technique was used to generate shallow water bathymetry charts from the Rosslare area in Ireland, and results from this activity are shown in Figures 20-24. Examples of data from the CLAMS system are shown in Figures 13-14, and application of CLAMS data in the Irish GIS for coastal zone management in Figure 15.

WP4: User assessment, conclusions and recommendations

Norwegian users

User assessment by a specific user: The Fedje VTS Centre

The Fedje Vessel Traffic Service (VTS) is responsible for guiding the tankers in and out from the two important oil ports Mongstad and Sture. Mongstad and Sture have more than 2000 ship calls every year. The tankers have to cross the north-south ship lane and go through narrow straits to enter Mongstad or Sture. During strong winds and high waves the steering of the tankers will be difficult. The tankers also sometimes experience strong currents up to 2 m/s 5 to 6 miles off Fedje. As the tankers have to reduce speed when they approach the passages, they can drift off their track.

According to the pilots at Fedje VTS it is of great importance to have accurate short term forecasts of wind and waves. DNMI provides the Fedje VTS with wind and wave forecasts, and the quality of these forecasts is good, but it can be improved by more observations both from ground and from satellites and data from high resolution numerical models. This has been demonstrated in the COASTMON project by use of a ground based wave radar, SAR wave spectra and a high resolution wave model.

But the pilots experience is that the most dangerous situations occur when the tankers goes into areas with unexpected strong currents. At the moment Fedje VTS does not receive current information on a regular basis. Some information about currents can be obtained by monitoring fronts and eddies with use of SAR data and infra-red satellite data. However it is not possible to directly determine the currents from the satellite data. Therefore data from numerical models and ground based measurements are necessary for monitoring and forecasting currents. A monitoring and forecasting system for currents in the Fedje area will be tested out in the MAST III project EuroROSE in February and March 2000. A High-Frequency radar will be used to measure surface current fields and ocean wave directional spectra. The physical mechanism behind is backscattering from a moving rough surface. The radar data will cover an area up to 50x50 km. The radar data will be combined with data from numerical models with horisontal resolution down to 1 km.

General evaluation of COASTMON products

In Norwegian waters the following satellite data products have been used in the COASTMON project

1. High-resolution wind fields from SAR.

Satellite based Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) measurements so far from ERS 1 / ERS-2 have been shown to provide wind speed data with an accuracy of ± 2 m/s. The SAR has clear advantages for high spatial resolution wind field mapping since it is independent of daylight and clouds. Wind retrieval from SAR will become very important from year 2000, since ENVISAT will carry SAR (which provide wind fields over 500 km swaths), but no wind scatterometer. Wind maps generated from SAR will be able to provide spatial information about the wind with a resolution of 400 m. SAR wind maps provide a synoptic estimate over the area covered by the SAR images. The limitation is the time resolution which is too coarse with current satellite systems. The estimates are instanteneous and not averaged over a time interval, for example 10 minutes which is common in traditional wind observations. SAR wind estimates should therefore be used

in combination with in situ wind measurements and synoptic fields from atmospheric models. Accurate measurements of wind in coastal regions is important because wind estimates from models can have errors due to topographic effects. In addition to better wind measurements, SAR wind can be used to calculate synoptic wind energy maps for coastal regions which can be used by wind energy companies in the planning of wind mill sites.

2. SAR wave spectra in coastal regions.

SAR has proven to be a useful data source to estimate wave spectra in the ocean, showing direction and wavelength of the long wave fields (wavenumber spectra), typically above 100 m. Techniques to use SAR wave spectra in operational wave forecasting has previously been developed. In COASTMON, SAR wave spectra have been estimated in near coastal regions and the SAR imaging mechanisms have been studied. The advantage of SAR images in near coastal regions is the capability to resolve structures in the wave field caused by shallow waters and topographic features. Different swell systems can be observed and processes such as refraction and wave breaking can be identified. Fine resolution SAR images from RADARSAT (pixel size down to 10 m) were tested in the Fedje region in combination with wave measurements from a coastal radar. Operational weather forecasting is the main user of these data. SAR images can provide more accurate and higher resolution wave information in near coastal regions compared to wave models. The capability to map waves synoptically makes SAR a useful complementary system to wave buoys, wave radars and models.

3. Mapping of eddies and ocean fronts

SAR is a useful complementary system to infrared and optical imaging of ocean eddies and fronts. The SAR imaging capability of these features is unaffected by cloud and daylight, but limited by wind speed. The observation of fronts, eddies and other features at the sea surface is possible at wind speeds below approximately 10 m/s. At higher wind speed the SAR signature is dominated by wind-wave imaging, masking out ocean fronts and other features. Ocean fronts and eddies are important for several reasons: maximum current velocity, temperature gradients, and areas of convergence and divergence are associated with these features. Areas of maximum current speed are important to observe for offshore industry for design and operations of floating platforms and for navigation of large tankers. Temperature fronts are important for living marine resources with impact on fisheries and aquaculture. Sea surface temperature can be observed with infrared radiometer data from satellites such as NOAA AVHRR. Ocean fronts can also be associated with changes in water colour which can be observed by optical satellite images. Water colour is an important parameter which can be used to measure chlorophyll and sediments in the upper water masses. Optical and infrared data are limited by clouds and cannot be used regularly in monitoring in Norwegian waters. Therefore, SAR used in combination with optical and infrared data gives optimal information about fronts and eddies.

4. Oil slick monitoring

SAR is a powerful tool to observe natural and man-made slicks at the ocean surface. Oil spills from ships, coastal plants and oil platforms can be identified in SAR imagery during moderate to low wind speed. In Norway an operational SAR oil spill monitoring service is established which is used by the Pollution Control Authority as a supplement to aircraft surveys. In an operational SAR monitoring service it is important to discriminate between

man-made and natural slicks, because there are many natural phenomena at the sea surface which are similar to an oil spill. Methods to analyse SAR images and discriminate between different slick signatures was developed [Espedal, 1998] with partial support from COASTMON. Surface slick monitoring is currently based on ERS SAR data, but wideswath SAR from RADARSAT and ENVISAT will improve the capability to monitor coastal regions significantly.

Irish users

Assessment of End-Users Responses

Three meetings were held with potential end-users. Information was sent to several organisations who expressed interest in the products of the project but were unable to attend the meetings; these included the Irish Meteorological Office, the Irish Marine Data Centre and the Dublin Port Authority. At the meetings the main COASTMON products were discussed: the BAS trials for Ireland; the relevance of CLAMS derived information for Irish users; and the use of SAR imagery for deriving wave spectra on specific dates. Dr Kees Mastenbroek (ARGOSS) attended these meetings to explain the methodology used to derive the information.

Meeting 1: Cork 14.30 Thursday 4th March 1999

- Tom Sexton, Port of Cork Engineer (interested in BAS for harbour management)
- Dr. Mark Duffy, Nautical Enterprise Centre (interested in wind and wave climate information)
- Brian Holmes, Hydraulics and Maritime Research Centre (interested in wind and wave climate information)

Tom Sexton felt that while the products were interesting, the failure of the BAS trial in Cork harbour, due to the lack of strong tidal currents (1 knot) over a wide area (25–30m), meant that the technique was not relevant to his organisation. He said that operational shipping needed information at a resolution of 3m rather than 30m. Kees Mastenbroek replied that this system was used in Holland for macro-scale surveying rather than strategic navigation. Its benefit is that it identifies where detailed surveying is required. Tom Sexton wanted to know how BAS compared financially with traditional surveying methods. Kees Mastenbroek said that in areas of non-crucial importance the amount of direct surveying could be significantly reduced, to the extent that the Dutch surveying fleet is being reduced due to a more focused approach to surveying since the introduction of the BAS technique. With a swath width of roughly 100km per image and a repeat cycle of three days the system is relatively cheap to use once it has been set up.

With regard to the altimeter and scatterometer wind and wave information, the off-shore nature of these data limit their applicability to harbour management.

Mark Duffy stated that the BAS product is of direct benefit to the activities of the NEC: specifically in detecting the movement (high-resolution changes in z) of large sub-tidal sand-waves and sandunes. The movement of these sedimentary bedforms with changing prevailing tides/currents can ultimately lead to the development of hazards to shipping e.g. around the Kish Bank in the Irish Sea. Regular mapping of the changes in macro-scale bedforms could prove a beneficial overlay to the next series of vector ECDIS charts to be published (ultimately forming a hydrographic tool). However, he stated that a strong limitation to the application of the BAS system in Ireland is the requirement of relatively fast currents ($>0.5\text{ms}^{-1}$) to have a sufficient change in speed proportional to depth for there to be a detectable difference.

He was interested in the applicability of the CLAMS system to areas such as the Irish Sea with restricted basins and minimum fetch. Kees Mastenbroek replied that the system had been designed for deep ocean sea state and could not resolve waves with a wavelength less than 100m. Mark Duffy replied that this was too large for the Irish Sea with wind generated

short wavelength waves. Mark Duffy enquired about its applicability to the North Sea. Kees Mastenbroek replied that the system assumes that the bathymetry is uniform over the study area. In the North Sea this assumption is not valid so lots of readings would have to be used. Mark Duffy then asked whether this meant that the information available on the CLAMS system about the Irish Sea was inaccurate. Kees Mastenbroek replied that the information must be used in context. It should optimally be used as offshore information to feed into near-shore models. Mark Duffy stated that inshore or shallow seas are invariably the regions that wave height and wind conditions are of most interest (to the NEC) when it comes to maritime operations e.g. shipping or dealing with oil spills. He identified another limitation to its use by NEC in the inability to determine the orthogonal direction of propagation (can only derive the direction perpendicular to the crest - which could of course be two directions).

With regard to the SAR imagery derived wave spectra, Mark Duffy wanted to know had the information been calibrated by buoy readings. Kees Mastenbroek responded that the altimeter based wave height information was very accurate and the measurement of the length of a wave from SAR imagery is very accurate.

Brian Holmes felt that while the BAS trials were not directly of relevance to his work in the HMRC, they would be of great interest to his colleague Dr James Murphy who works in the area of coastal protection. He felt that while the information was of interest, details such as accuracy, repetition, validation etc. would require clarification.

Brian Holmes was very interested in hearing about the altimeter and scatterometer derived wave information. He felt that with the advent of SAR and the prospect of full spectral information this area showed great promise. He believed that the ability to record to the shoreline also boosted the usefulness of such records. Time restrictions at the meeting prevented him from discussing the technology in as much detail as he would have liked. At some time in the future he would like to discuss how the early correction algorithms can be verified with sea truth records. As with the bathymetric output (and all space borne recording systems), he stated that care must be taken in these evaluations by considering the return track period and geographical area regularly covered. In the open ocean wave conditions are considered homogenous over considerable sea areas. Close to shore they can change dramatically in only a few kilometers. The shallow water coastal zone is of course where waves impact most with human endeavour. He stated that the advantage SAR imagery has over other sources of this information is that it is a true measure, albeit remotely as opposed to one that was analytically or numerically derived. Brian Holmes would like to be kept informed of any further developments of this project.

Meeting 2: Cork 9.30 Friday 5th March 1999

- Jerry Sutton, Coastal Resources Centre (interested in wind and wave climate information for RACER project)
- Tom Hubbard, Coastal Resources Centre (interested in wind/wave climate information for RACER project)
- Dr. Ignatio Lozano-Gonzalez, Coastal Resources Centre (interested in wind and wave climate information for STORMINESS project)

Jerry Sutton felt that the products demonstrated had potential relevance to both the RACER project in relation to oceanographic parameters and also more general interest in terms of

bathymetry.

He felt that the wind/wave climate product would be useful to the RACER project and could be supplied by ARGOSS from their archive for the region of interest. However, the actual benefit of incorporating this information with ship reports and pilotage data would have to be assessed before the cost of acquiring the data could be justified. In addition, the data would have to be further processed upon receipt for correlation with existing sources. He is currently considering this option.

The inherent problems with SAR and scatterometer derived wind/wave spectral data stem from the effects of land influence, rendering such approaches redundant in the Irish Sea context (the RACER project area) given its width.

He felt that the discussion regarding SAR derived bathymetry indicated that useful data are only obtainable under limited meteorological and tidal conditions. The current instrumentation and complex hydrodynamic techniques used to relate surface backscatter to underlying topography yield accuracies of approx 0.3-0.5 m at best, under optimal conditions, which limits the use to broad reconnaissance type bathymetric applications. However there may be some potential applications in relation to monitoring temporal and spatial evolution of offshore sand and gravel bodies off the East coast given the relative frequency of repeat coverage of SAR swaths.

Tom Hubbard felt that the footprint of the remote sensors is too large to be of much use in the Irish Sea. If it cannot go closer than 20 km to land this means for the RACER project it would give a small track in the middle - if it could provide any information at all. The accuracy of the altimeter and scatterometer derived wave height and wind speed would give a good overview of the conditions. He would be interested in looking at wave height against wind speed. However, it seems that the two measurements are not available in the same place at the same time so he might not be able to compare them. The RACER project wants to examine sea state scenarios and for this he wants to identify which conditions give rise to an unexpected and possibly dangerous sea state. The aim is to facilitate the interpretation of weather forecasts, for this purpose he needs wave direction, which does not appear to be available from a satellite source.

Meeting 3: Dublin 14.30 Friday 5th March 1999

- Dr. Gerard Farrell, Chief Engineer, Department of Marine and Natural Resources (DoMNR) (interested in BAS)
- Jim Casey, Engineer, (DoMNR) (interested in BAS)
- Noel O' Murchu, Engineer, (DoMNR) - (interested in BAS)

The Department of Marine and Natural Resources engineers found the BAS results for Rosslare very interesting. The Department may be interested in obtaining data for Rosslare in the future. They are interested in receiving information about other regions around Ireland where bathymetric data can be obtained using the BAS system. Deirdre Tobin will provide them with the seasonal maps of BAS suitability around Ireland.

They also found the presentation on the CLAMS wave climate assessment tool very interesting. The Department has wave buoys deployed on the 10 m and 20 m contour for the past 18 months and feel it would be interesting to compare actual results with CLAMS. However, this comparison would be restricted by the fact that the CLAMS system could not be used in regions

with short period waves. They are interested in ascertaining what cost would be involved in obtaining wave information every 6 or 12 months from CLAMS in some inshore location on the 10m or 20m contour along the West coast of Ireland.

Comparison of end products with initial user-requirements

In the original Irish user-requirements workshops the requirements in Table 14 were identified.

Table 14: Requirements for different types of users in Ireland.

User-type	Sensor	Requirement
Naval Service	SAR	Pollution monitoring Detection of discharge ballast Coastal erosion monitoring Sediment tracking
Harbour Authorities	Optical	Sediment flows
Harbour Authorities	SAR	Shallow water bathymetric change
Harbour Authorities	SAR	Wind/wave height Vessel detection
Coastal Engineers	SAR / Altimeter	Wave climate data
Marine Infrastructure	SAR	Vessel detection Swell and wave data

Pollution Monitoring: As part of the COASTMON project SAR and optical imagery were obtained in an attempt to monitor an oil spill event in Cork Harbour on the 4th of November 1997. Due to cloud cover and low wind conditions the oil spill was not visible on the imagery. More details of this exercise are available on Annex 1 of the mid-term report.

Detection of Discharge Ballast: Due to the infrequency of the SAR imagery coverage (1 image every 30 days we decided that this application could not be realistically undertaken, as real-time or near-real time imagery would be required for this product.

Coastal Erosion Monitoring: The project area was originally restricted to the Cork Harbour Area where minimal coastal erosion occurs. Coastal erosion in Ireland is mainly concentrated on the East Coast. Further work could be undertaken using SAR imagery over time to identify coastal change in this area.

Sediment Tracking: Moss imagery was obtained for the South West Coast of Ireland. Sediment flow was visible from this image and ARGOSS calculated turbidity for selected locations (ref mid-term report). This image and turbidity information was shown to the Fisheries Research Centre.

Shallow Water Bathymetry: This was initially undertaken for Cork Harbour. However, the location proved unsuitable and further trials were held in Rosslare where the process was successful. A series of seasonal BAS suitability maps were produced to identify where the process could potentially be used. This product was demonstrated to various harbour authorities and coastal engineers. Their comments are outlined in the "Assessment of End-Users Responses" section above.

Wind/Wave Data: Altimeter results were integrated into a wave climate atlas, produced by the HMRC based on WAM data. Wave climate information for areas off Cork were calculated

from SAR imagery and supplied to the HMRC for comparison with their inshore wave model. Scatterometer and Altimeter data were integrated into an operational planning tool in a GIS (ref mid-term report). CLAMS and these wind/wave products were discussed at the end user workshops (cfr. the "Assessment of End-Users Responses" section above.)

Vessel Detection: As with the ballast discharge application, vessel detection required near-real time coverage. This product is not viable from SAR at its current repeat cycle rate.

In addition to the user-requirements identified at the initial user-requirements workshops, the use of remote sensing images for algal bloom monitoring was examined for the area off the South West coast of Ireland. This is discussed in detail in the mid-term report. End-user responses to this information are outlined in the "Assessment of End-Users Responses" section above.

Conclusions

The BAS results were of interest to the Rosslare Harbour Master and the Department of Marine and Natural Resources Engineers. As a macro-scale method of monitoring where re-survey is required it may have a role to play in Ireland. However, due to the low level of current off the north and West coast the potential usage of this technique is restricted to the SE coast. Seasonal maps produced using the COASTMON GIS, were used to give a rough indication of areas where the BAS technique is likely to be applicable. Only a limited number of locations are identified in these maps. Due to the lack of availability of high resolution current and wind information, the areas identified as suitable are indicative only. If the BAS system were to be considered as a national monitoring technique, higher resolution information would have to be obtained upon which to assess site suitability.

The CLAMS database was of interest to several of the end-user groups. However, the fact that the system could not be used in regions with short period waves seemed to be a restriction on its potential use in the Irish Sea. The RACER project team is considering making use of altimeter data in conjunction with ship sightings and pilotage information. The Department of Marine and Natural Resources engineers are interested in comparing this information against buoy data. The HMRC found the comparison of this data with the WAM numerical model of interest and would be interested in becoming involved in further development of this product.

The Fisheries Research Centre was very interested in the potential to map an algal bloom extent using the NOAA images. They would be interested in obtaining further images in the future.

Recommendations

Trials should be undertaken comparing the wind/wave data from the CLAMS system with the data from the Department of Marine and Natural Resources newly placed buoys.

The seasonal suitability maps for BAS should be refined to try and identify more precisely exactly which areas this technique could be applied to.

Collaboration should be established with the Department of Marine and Natural Resources for further trials of the BAS system.

The collaboration with the RACER project should be followed up, and wind/wave data supplied if required.

The possibility of using SAR imagery for monitoring coastal erosion on the East Coast of Ireland should be examined.

Links with the JRC, specifically the marine section should be strengthened. This project has identified that these are potential uses of remote sensing in Ireland. However, the recurring theme of the end-user workshops was that there is a requirement for inshore information. Greater collaboration is required with the JRC to establish which techniques are most applicable to the Irish coastal community, and with which remote sensing organisations future collaboration should be established.

Irish end-users awareness of the applications of remote sensing data is limited. Training courses and further projects such as COASTMON should be established to broaden this awareness.

Dutch users

Product 2. Detection of swell using SAR imagery in coastal regions

The technique of extracting detailed information from SAR imagery on swell as it travels through a coastal regions is very powerful. The examples generated as part of the COASTMON project show that the technique is viable. However, at this moment little is known about the capabilities of the technique. Users agreed that it could be a useful tool to validate and calibrate near shore wave models. One limitation of the technique is the availability and selection of imagery. The technique can only be applied when an appreciable amount of swell is entering the region of interest. It is not straightforward to select the SAR images that coincide with such an event, without actually ordering them. Before a larger community of users can be interested in this emerging technique its accuracy and reliability should be established. This could be done by analysing imagery in coastal areas that are exposed to ocean swell, and spectral in-situ wave measurements are available.

Product 3. Wind and wave climatology

Users were generally enthousiastic about the capabilities offered by the on-line wave climate service CLAMS. The effort to provide spectral wave climate information was appreciated very much. Apart from some small imperfections that can be dealt with quite easily, the following limitations of the present system were mentioned: (1) The swell information derived with the SPRA algorithm developed in the COASTMON project has an 180 degree ambiguity in the propagation direction. This causes some confusion with users, and is generally perceived as a feature that should be dealt with. A possible solution could be to use collocated wave model output to eliminate the ambiguity. (2) The energy density spectra derived from the SAR measurements with the SPRA scheme show a gap between the longest wind waves and the shortest swell waves resolved by the SAR. For many applications this renders the data less than perfect, as it is difficult to derive integral parameters from the present spectra. This problem may also be resolved by merging the SAR derived spectra with numerical wave model output.

III. CONCLUSIONS

This work has demonstrated the feasibility of using selected EO-data for the COASTMON application sites.

The results showed that:

- Useful data products for coastal and marine operations can be generated from several existing EO data (SAR, altimeter, AVHRR, etc.), given that certain meteorological or other conditions imposed by the specific algorithm are met.
- SAR is capable of providing high resolution images suited for coastal monitoring, and has the advantage of being independent of daylight and clouds. Examples of products that can be developed from SAR data are high resolution wind fields, wave products, detection of frontal structures and monitoring of oil spills. The main limiting factor is the insufficient temporal and spatial resolution provided by today's satellites.
- The radar altimeter is well suited for providing climatological wind and wave data on large and regional scales, but its spatial resolution does not suffice for many activities in the coastal zone, e.g. harbour monitoring.
- Visual/IR sensors are useful for monitoring of algal blooms and water quality parameters, but their use is limited by clouds implying that temporal coverage is poor. On the other hand the spatial resolution (1 km) is adequate for such monitoring purposes.
- Users can be grouped in two main categories: operational and occasional users who need data for planning. The first need 'contionous' data in near real-time, while the latter may be satisfied with climatological data. More satellites are needed to provide sufficient coverage in the coastal zone.
- The users can also be categorized into: those needing local, very detailed information and those needing regional coverage but at a lower resolution. The first group need high resolution data, i.e. on the order of meters, while the other group can do with data on the order of a few kilometers.
- Spatial resolution is adequate for SAR and AVHRR data, while the altimeter data are too coarse neas the coast.
- Temporal resolution is poor for customers who need frequent data coverage.

Demands for meeting users' requirements in the future:

- More SAR satellites and improved SAR technology (polarmetric, multi-mode, and multi-channel).
- Hyperspectral data with high resolution.
- Further development of algorithms and customized software tools for specific user groups.

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IV. ANNEXES

A. Copies of specific deliverables

The following reports from the project are enclosed:

1. Jenkins et al. (1997), "COASTMON - Metocean and coastal zone monitoring in harbour regions using satellite radar. WP1: Identification of gaps between current monitoring technology and user requirements", NERSC Technical Report no. 135.
2. Jenkins et al. (1999), "COASTMON - Metocean and coastal zone monitoring in harbour regions using satellite radar. WP2: Development of improved EO data products", NERSC Technical Report no. 156.

B. Reports on workshops

It was decided at the kick-off meeting to hold national user workshops, to ensure that the maximum number of potential users would attend.

The following workshops were held:

- Norway:
 - 21 May 1997: First Norwegian user workshop held at NERSC.
 - 19 January 1999: COASTMON user demonstration, Høvik, Norway, presented by A.D. Jenkins.
- The Netherlands:
 - 05 May 1997: First Dutch user workshop held at ARGOSS.
 - 29 October 1998: Evaluation workshop, Zwolle, The Netherlands organised by ARGOSS.
- Ireland:
 - 25 June 1997: First Irish user workshop held at CRC.
 - 4-5 March 1999: Evaluation workshops, Ireland, organised by CRC.

Minutes from the workshops are attached to the report. These were published on the project's web pages as soon as they became available, and were free for everyone to download.

C. Published material

C.1 Conference proceedings and presentations

- Jenkins, A.D., S. Sandven, L. Pettersson, T. Hamre, M. Miles, K. Mastenbroek, M. Reistad, B.Å. Hjøllø, N. Connolly, E. O’Leary and D. Tobin, "MetOcean and Coastal Zone Monitoring In Harbour Regions Using Satellite Radar", in Proceedings of th 27th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of the Environment, pp. 151–154. June 8–12, 1998, Tromsø, Norway. The paper was presented by A.D. Jenkins.
- COASTMON was presented by A.D. Jenkins at the "Earth Observation for Customers" workshop in Lisbon, Portugal, 2-3 July 1998.
Title of presentation: "MetOcean and Coastal Zone Monitoring in Harbour Regions Using Satellite Radar (COASTMON project)". A PostScript version of this presentation is available from the project’s web pages, see e.g. the News page.
- Mastenbroek, C., Spectral wave climate data from space-borne SAR. Proceedings WMO conference on the provision and engineering/operational application of ocean wave data, 21-25 September 1998, WMO-TD-No. 938, 304-309.
- Mastenbroek, C., Spectral wave climate data from spaceborne SAR. Proceedings CEOS working group on calibration validation SAR subgroup, 3-6 February 1998, ESTEC,17-25.

C.2 Journal papers

- Espedal, H. A. and Wahl, W. (1999), Satellite SAR oil spill detection using wind history, *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, **20**(1):49–65.
- Furevik, B., and Korsbakken, E., Comparison of Synthetic Aperture Radar and Scatterometer derived wind speed during the ERS Tandem Phase, Submitted to J. Geophys. Res., May 1999.
- Korsbakken, E., Johannessen, J. A., and Johannessen, O. M. (1998), Coastal wind field retrievals from ERS synthetic aperture radar images, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **103**(C4):7857–7874.
- Mastenbroek (1998) High resolution wind fields from the ERS SAR. *Earth Observation Quarterly*, 59, 20-22.
- Mastenbroek and De Valk (1999) A semi-parametric algorithm to retrieve ocean wave spectra from SAR. Submitted to J. Geophys. Res.
- Voorrips, Mastenbroek and Hansen (1999) Retrieval of ocean wave spectra from ERS-SAR: a validation study. In preparation.

C.3 Technical reports

- Technical reports from WP 1 and WP 2: see Appendix A.

D. Publicity material

Results from the project has been disseminated through:

- User workshops in the three partner countries (cfr. Section IV.B)
- Presentations at conferences and symposia (cfr. Section IV.C.1 and poster presented at the FARGIS/POSEIDON seminar (Figures 44-45))
- Scientific literature (cfr. Section IV.C.2/3)
- The project's web pages (cfr. Section IV.E)

E. Presentation of project web pages

The home page of the project can be found at:

<http://www.nrsc.no/COASTMON/>

This provides links to the different partners and products, news and some of the delivered reports. These pages will reside on their respective sites for a year after the project ended, i.e. until the end of March 2000. Hardcopies of sample web pages for the project are enclosed.

F. Definitions, acronyms, abbreviations

Term	Explanation
ARGOSS	Advisory and Research Group on Geo Observation Systems and Services
ATSR	Along Track Scanning Radiometer
AVHRR	Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer
CZM	Coastal Zone Management
DNMI	The Norwegian Meteorological Institute
EOM	Earth Observation Model
ERIM	Environmental Research Institute of Michigan
ERS-1,2	Earth Resource Satellite no. 1 and 2.
ESA	European Space Agency
GIS	Geographic Information System
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
GTS	Global Telecommunication System
HIRLAM	High Resolution Limited Area Model
ICAMS	Integrated Coastal Analysis and Monitoring System
ICSU	The International Council for Scientific Unions
IGBP	International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme
IOC	The Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
MOS	Modular Optoelectronic Scanner
LOICZ	Land Ocean Interaction in Coastal Zones
NERSC	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
RACER	Risk Assessment and Collaborative Emergency Response in the Irish Sea
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SeaWiFS	Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor
SWA	SAR Wind Algorithm
CRC-URR	Coastal Resources Centre, University College Cork, Ireland
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
VLCCs	Very large crude-oil carriers
VTs	Vessel Traffic Service
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation